

Uncovering the Applications, Developments, and Future Research Directions of the Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS): A Systematic Literature Review

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Supplementary information

APPENDIX A.

Table A.1. Descriptive summary of the articles analyzed in the systematic literature review.

Title	Country/region of application	Type of study	Research gap addressed/Paper objective	Addition - modification to original model	Accessibility to modified model	Data availability	Temporal resolution	Spatial resolution	Policy recommendations	Future research proposed	Reference
Assessing the relative impacts of maximum investment rate and temporal detail in capacity expansion models applied to power systems	Europe	Modelling	Systematic comparison of the impact of flexibility requirement representation and maximum investment rate on capacity expansion model outcomes	Power transmission module based on an enforcement of Kirchoff's current law. It includes new parameters, variables, and constraints.	Mathematical modelling is available at the article in the Appendix Code implementation is not available Code version: Pyomo	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: From 24 to 336 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2050	17 regions	The primary concern confronting power system planners might shift away from deliberating which low-carbon technology or mix of technologies to deploy, and instead focus more on accelerating the implementation of all presently accessible low-carbon technologies.	Additional comprehensive studies employing alternative model frameworks are required to confirm that the solutions recommended by capacity expansion models can guarantee adequacy, stability, and inertia, or align with internal network constraints.	[113]
Techno-economic dataset and assumptions for long-term energy systems modelling in the Dominican Republic (2024-2050)	Dominican Republic	Data article	Open dataset designed to create an energy system model of the Dominican Republic for energy planning in the power and transport sectors	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Timeseries data: 2024-2050	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	[99]
Modelling Policy Pathways to Maximise Renewable Energy Growth and Investment in the Democratic Republic	Democratic Republic of Congo	Case study	Develop, assess, and propose potential national policies for the government of the DRC aimed at maximizing growth and investment in renewable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 8 timeslices	1 region	(1) Implement financial incentives to stimulate the development of renewable energy sources in the DRC.	Evaluation of the effects on the policy pathways under scenarios of alternative demand projections and local cost inputs.	[65]

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of the Congo Using OSeMOSYS (Open Source Energy Modelling System)			energy generation over the coming decades				Modelling horizon: 2021-2070		(2) Introduce taxes on fossil fuel energy production. (3) Reassess the emphasis placed on hydropower. (4) Promote the DRC as a promising market for solar home systems.		
Pathways to Clean Energy Transition in Indonesia's Electricity Sector with Open-Source Energy Modelling System Modelling (OSeMOSYS)	Indonesia	Case study	Assessment of Indonesia's opportunities and potential to achieve low carbon ambition in the energy sector and identify long-term pathways for the energy transition in Indonesia	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 8 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2020-2070	1 region	Phasing out coal-powered technologies and deploying new renewables must happen simultaneously. Additionally, reaching net zero by 2050 offers the best cost-benefit alternative under the scenarios evaluated. According to this target, Indonesia must adopt and deploy 87% renewable energy before 2030 and achieve 100% renewables by 2070	Further detailed analyses on costs, flexibility implications, and alternative technologies, advocating for in-depth cost analyses, flexibility and sensitivity assessments, and exploring alternative scenarios involving clean technologies like carbon capture and storage (CCS)	[50]
Evidence-Based Policymaking: Insights and Recommendations for the Implementation of Clean Energy Transition Pathways for Kenya's Power Sector	Kenya	Case study	Inform policy that integrates Kenya's diverse energy objectives, incorporating both the expansion of renewable energy sources and the rising energy demand	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 8 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2050	1 region	Policy alignment, increased wind power production, energy efficiency penetration, finance and investment securement, the development of geothermal technologies, power transmission, and distribution improvements should be prioritised	Development of a whole-system assessment encompassing all sectors, including cooking, transport, and land use, is essential. Additionally, conducting flexibility evaluations would be crucial. Qualitative studies for stakeholder engagement in energy studies should also be considered	[71]
Assessing the role of low-emission hydrogen: A techno-economic database for hydrogen pathways modelling	Colombia	Data article	Open techno-economic dataset covering key technologies across the hydrogen supply chain, ranging from production to end-use applications. Professional and academic communities can use this dataset to develop energy planning models, particularly emphasizing hydrogen pathways	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Timeseries data: 2021-2050	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	[100]

Energy transition implications for Bolivia. Long-term modelling with short-term assessment of future scenarios	Bolivia	Case study - Methodology	Extend previous research by broadening its scope and enhancing modelling efforts undertaken for Bolivia. It introduces a soft-linking methodology that integrates long-term (OSeMOSYS) and short-term (Dispa-SET) models, which were previously studied independently. Furthermore, it emphasizes the novelty of using open-source tools exclusively, making them easily accessible for other researchers or institutions.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Data will be made available on request.	Intrayear resolution: 6 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2020-2055	1 region	Transitioning to renewable energy is now more economically viable compared to traditional fossil fuel-based systems. However, substantial upfront investments are necessary, highlighting the need for complementary research on financing. Although the policies simulated in this study fall short of achieving full decarbonization, increasing carbon pricing demonstrates potential for further emissions reductions.	(1) Spatial disaggregation to capture the expansion of the transmission network, regional availability of resources and system evolution at subnational level (2) Modelling of conversion routes for alternative fuels, such as hydrogen biofuels or carbon capture (3) Increase sectoral disaggregation to explore detailed end-use requirements and sector-specific policies	[75]
Addressing Challenges in Long-Term Strategic Energy Planning in LMICs: Learning Pathways in an Energy Planning Ecosystem	Not applicable	Methodology	Introduction of a novel strategy for tackling significant global issues in long-term energy planning, specifically targeting low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). The proposed approach involves the establishment and evaluation of an international enabling environment, a delivery ecosystem, and a community of practice. These elements are seamlessly integrated into operational frameworks, resulting in the attainment of four self-sustaining capacity-development objectives.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	It is recommended that policymakers prioritize the development of an energy planning ecosystem to ensure future energy planning exercises are nationally owned, inclusive, robust, and transparent.	Future research and practical initiatives should concentrate on broadening the accessibility of programs, assessing the long-term effects of learning pathways, enhancing institutional capacity, and enriching skill sets	[38]
A multicriteria modeling approach for evaluating power generation scenarios under uncertainty: The case of green hydrogen in Greece	Greece	Case study - Methodology	Energy planning decision-support framework that incorporates an innovative integration of an energy-system optimization model with various multi-criteria analysis methods and regret measures. This framework facilitates the identification of the optimal rate of adoption for anticipated, transformative technologies within the power sector, while also	Not applicable	Not applicable	Data will be made available on request.	Intrayear resolution: 24 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2050	1 region	(1) Policies for green hydrogen should consider storage capacity to minimize grid curtailment and boost clean power use. Neglecting this may increase fossil fuel reliance, hindering a comprehensive green strategy. Hydrogen storage could reduce the reliance on more expensive renewables	(1) Modelling of additional green hydrogen uses (e.g., transport) (2) OSeMOSYS soft-linking with a macroeconomic model to evaluate the socioeconomic implications of the transition to a green hydrogen economy (3) Sensitivity analysis against the criteria weights used in the MCDM methods	[88]

			considering decision makers' attitudes towards uncertainty						such as geothermal or hydro. (2) Regarding the adoption of green hydrogen in the power sector, there's a critical juncture where decision-makers may prefer faster diffusion rates up to a certain point. Conservative decision-makers might opt for policies with faster green hydrogen penetration, as these are less sensitive to uncertainties despite offering lower marginal returns.	(4) Implementation of alternative MCDM methods to incorporate risk behaviour into the analysis	
Informing sustainable energy policy in developing countries: An assessment of decarbonization pathways in Colombia using open energy system optimization modelling	Colombia	Case study	Development of an open energy system model to conduct decarbonization pathway assessment and energy planning in Colombia, enabling further collaboration between stakeholders and researchers	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: No timeslices Modelling horizon: 2021-2050	1 region	Renewable power generation, electrification of end-uses, carbon capture and storage (CCS), low-emission hydrogen as a fuel, and energy efficiency emerge as pivotal technologies for achieving decarbonization pathways. Integrated energy policy should promote enablers like diverse financing sources, the advancement of national green industry, collaborative research and development among institutions, local training and education initiatives, and shifts in consumer behaviour.	(1) Increase the temporal and regional resolutions of the model to obtain insights around geographical and intra-year evolution of the energy system (2) Incorporation of uncertainty quantification techniques such as robust optimization or stochastic programming (3) Evaluation of the fiscal and macroeconomic impacts of the decarbonization pathways (4) CLEWs-based modelling to capture the interlinkages between land, water, and energy towards the target of net zero	[77]
Role of the energy-carbon-economy nexus and CO2 abatement cost in supporting energy policy analysis: A multi-scenario analysis of the Java-Bali system	Indonesia	Case study	Analysis of the economic impacts on the energy and carbon nexus in the Java-Bali system to assess feasible strategies to support two policies, a new and renewable energy target and coal phase-out planning. An additional policy based on carbon tax is proposed through cost-benefit analysis	Not applicable	Not applicable	Data will be made available on request.	Intrayear resolution: No information Modelling horizon: 2021-2050	1 region	(1) Regulation for carbon limitations and taxes for power generation companies are required. (2) The government should promptly commit to leveraging nuclear energy and ensuring a sufficient supply of liquefied natural gas (LNG) at an accessible cost (3) It is imperative to explore alternatives for meeting demand	Evaluation of cost sensitivity and negative emission technologies modelling in the analysis	[64]

									projections by establishing interconnections with other islands that have abundant renewable energy sources		
A baseline long term technoeconomic electricity supply model for highly regulated fuel importing countries prone to shortages: Case of Jordan	Jordan	Case study	Assessment of a case study to consider the features of highly regulated fuel importing countries prone to shortages. This case explores the single primary supplier condition in Jordan expressed by a long-term contract to import natural gas from the Leviathan gas field. It also expands previous research efforts by focusing on the contractual aspects of the Jordanian power system.	Not applicable	Not applicable	The authors do not have permission to share data.	Intrayear resolution: 8 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2070	1 region	(1) Shorter long-term gas import agreements afford decision makers the flexibility to customize future contracts regarding pricing, lower and upper limits, ensuring they align with Jordan's best interests. (2) Diversifying the energy mix is key to establishing a financially efficient energy system. Vital to this endeavour is investment in wind and solar energy technologies. Additionally, diversifying the sources of natural gas imports in Jordan through multiple long-term agreements with various suppliers is imperative	(1) Modelling of storage technologies would enable to explore additional options under scenarios of high penetration of renewable energy (2) Inclusion of higher temporal resolution in terms of number of timeslices	[84]
Empowering Tomorrow's Problem Solvers: Nexus Thinking and CLEWs Modelling as a Pedagogical Approach to Wicked Problems	Not applicable	Pedagogical	Proposal of the use of Climate, Land, Energy, and Water (CLEWs) modelling as an innovative pedagogical tool to promote nexus thinking among students, applied to a higher education context in the form of a Masters' module for geography students.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Incorporating social-based modules for offering a well-balanced pedagogical approach alongside quantitative analysis. Examples include modules on the Anthropocene or climate change and society	[90]
Supporting energy system modelling in developing countries: Techno-economic energy dataset for open modelling of decarbonization pathways in Colombia	Colombia	Data article	Open dataset designed to create a whole energy system model of Colombia for energy planning and decarbonization pathways	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Timeseries data: 2021-2050	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	[101]
Hydropower and climate change, insights from the integrated water-	Drin Basin (Europe)	Modelling	(1) First application of an entire long-term electricity supply model for the Drin Basin with national detail and the focus on	Enhanced representation of hydropower plants and their	Mathematical modelling is available at the article in the Appendix	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 52 timeslices	4 regions	(1) This study reveals that the Albanian power system is more vulnerable to climate	Sensitivity analyses could explore the effects of various operational rules and electricity import prices. Further detail on the	[57]

energy modelling of the Drin Basin			<p>representation of the hydrocascade.</p> <p>(2) Detailed representation of the dam and its operational rules to explore the impact of changing conditions to ensure flood control.</p> <p>(3) Open methodology for long-term energy planning in other transboundary river basins</p>	<p>operational rules which allows exploring the impact of new rules</p> <p>Based on an alternative storage modelling [link]</p> <p>Introduction of the dimension of timeslice in a set of parameters and equations to capture the variation in each timeslice</p>	<p>Code implementation is available at [link]</p> <p>Code version: MathProg</p>		<p>Modelling horizon: 2020-2050</p>		<p>change compared to North Macedonia's.</p> <p>(2) Variable renewable energy presents an opportunity to mitigate climate change risks and enhance electricity supply security. Moreover, the energy sector can contribute significantly to reducing flood impacts and enhancing national resilience to extreme climate events.</p> <p>(3) An integrated water-energy management plan could aid dam operators in planning both short-term production and long-term flood control services.</p>	<p>impact of Skavica on other hydropower plants in the Albanian cascade could be provided once actual operational data from Skavica is available. Increasing time resolution, expanding storage modelling, and examining short-term dynamics of variable renewable energy investments and grid stability are areas for improvement. Additionally, future studies could broaden climate change projections and scenarios using different hydrological models to quantify uncertainties in climate change impacts.</p>	
Integration of high levels of electrolytic hydrogen production: Impact on power systems planning	Chile	Modelling	<p>(1) Propose a methodological framework for long-term planning using a customized adaptation of OSeMOSYS to design the integrated development and operation of a national electricity system coupled with an electrolytic Hydrogen Supply Chain (HSC).</p> <p>(2) Introduce a module to depict the provision of operational reserves via electricity consumption technologies, including the potential for reserve trading between regions and utilizing technologies with excess capacity to supply reserves.</p> <p>(3) Evaluate the effects of various HSC integration scenarios on the progression of a predominantly renewable national power system.</p>	<p>New parameters, variables, and constraints are proposed to explicitly specify the daily energy demand of a fuel.</p> <p>New equations and some proposed by Welsch et al. (2015), aimed at quantifying the supply of operational reserves, and incorporating the explicit representation of reserves trade between regions, the provision of reserves by electricity consumption technologies, and the provision of reserves by electricity consumption technologies with</p>	<p>Mathematical modelling and code implementation are available with subscription to Elsevier</p> <p>Code version: MathProg</p>	<p>Available with subscription to Elsevier [link]</p>	<p>Intrayear resolution: 96 timeslices</p> <p>Modelling horizon: 2018-2050</p>	4 regions	<p>(1) On-grid electrolytic hydrogen production proves more cost-effective than off-grid alternatives.</p> <p>(2) Synchronizing a seasonal hydrogen dispatch profile with photovoltaic availability improves system efficiency, reducing emissions and energy losses.</p> <p>(3) Inter-seasonal hydrogen storage is not cost-effective in most scenarios, except when ammonia serves as an energy carrier.</p> <p>(4) Integrating hydrogen supply chains into the power system increases electrical load, primarily met by photovoltaic capacity, but requires varying investments in technologies like concentrated solar power, wind, and pumped hydro+battery storage compared to a base system without hydrogen integration.</p>	<p>(1) Enhance temporal resolution to accurately capture the variability throughout a year of operation.</p> <p>(2) Conduct uncertainty assessment for input data to account for potential inaccuracies.</p> <p>(3) Perform an analysis to ascertain the criteria under which electrolytic hydrogen generated through direct grid connection can be labelled as "green hydrogen."</p>	[89]

				overloading capacity.							
Designing a zero-order energy transition model: How to create a new Starter Data Kit	Not applicable	Methodology	The development of a replicable and open-source approach for gathering and using energy system data aims to support credible energy modelling. This endeavour ensures the sustainability of dependable and precise data-driven modelling, facilitating well-informed policymaking. Such an approach holds value for various practitioners, including academics, civil servants, analysts, and policymakers.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	(1) Numerous model assumptions rely on generic values, presenting an opportunity for enhancement tailored to specific sectors, countries, or regions. (2) Expand the modelling scope to include additional temporal and geographic resolution, broader sectoral coverage, integration of new technologies such as storage, and analysis of specific policy assumptions.	[98]
Modelling the Optimal Electricity Mix for Togo by 2050 Using OSeMOSYS	Togo	Case study	The study involves modelling the electricity mix while considering the existing direction of Togolese energy policy, aiming to project outcomes up to 2050. Its objective is to initiate discourse on the matter by examining, with defined assumptions, the future trajectory of Togo's electricity mix. Additionally, it investigates the policy choices and investments necessary to fulfil both national and international objectives concerning sustainable energy and climate change.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 8 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2022-2050	1 region	Solar PV is a crucial element in the electricity mix, with its proportion ranging from 56% to 62% by 2030 and increasing to 65% to 91% by 2050. Financial estimates indicate that a tenfold increase in investment is required by 2030 to maintain the current trajectory or facilitate a strategic shift.	A long-term assessment of flexibility of the power system.	[78]
Phasing-out of coal from the energy system in Mauritius	Mauritius	Case study	This paper aims to offer policy insights to assist authorities in achieving their objective of phasing out coal usage for electricity generation by the year 2030 in Mauritius, analyzing the deployment of a more diversified renewable energy mix.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Data will be made available on request.	Intrayear resolution: 96 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2040	1 region	The short-term policy priorities for facilitating the coal phase-out by 2030 would require investments in grid stabilization to accommodate increased variable renewable energy, particularly grid-connected distributed generation solar photovoltaic systems. Furthermore, to mitigate the intermittent nature of renewable energy sources, investments in reliable dispatchable	No limitations have been declared.	[67]

									technologies such as hybrid renewable systems, biomass, and waste-to-energy plants are essential.		
Techno-economic data and assumptions for long-term energy systems modelling in Viet Nam	Vietnam	Data article	This article presents key information regarding input data and assumptions crucial for long-term energy planning in Vietnam. The provided data can serve as a valuable resource for academics, consultants, or government officials seeking to conduct further energy systems modelling in Vietnam or the broader Asian region.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Timeseries data: 2015-2050	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	[102]
Long-term electricity supply modelling in the context of developing countries: The OSeMOSYS-LEAP soft-linking approach for Ethiopia	Ethiopia	Case study - Methodology	This study conducts a quantitative analysis of Ethiopia's future power generation sector within the broader context of developing nations. This analysis aims to offer an accurate representation of electricity systems in developing countries, taking into account unique features such as traditional energy consumption, the informal economy, urban-rural disparities, low electrification rates, supply shortages, data and skill requirements. Additionally, it involves examining the impact of decentralized power options and energy efficiency policies.	Not applicable	Not applicable	The authors do not have permission to share data.	Intrayear resolution: 6 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2018-2050	1 region	(1) Ethiopia should invest in renewable energy resources, with hydropower continuing to be significant alongside alternative sources such as wind, natural gas, geothermal, solar PV, and CSP. (2) Addressing hydro dependence requires enhancing power system resilience through fuel-based dispatchable generation, cross-border electric power exchange, demand response management, and infrastructure redesign. (3) Policymakers should devise effective policies supporting technological and efficiency innovations in the power sector. (4) Ethiopia needs to develop its expertise in all renewable energy resources to effectively deploy and manage future technologies. (5) Policymakers are urged to allocate sufficient land for potential development of solar PV, wind, and CSP farms.	(1) Enhance temporal resolution to accurately assess the effects of variable renewable energy on the future power generation mix. (2) Employ multi-regional modeling to conduct in-depth analysis of electricity access, renewable energy penetration, overall system costs, and identify optimal locations for renewable and grid development while addressing network bottlenecks.	[80]

									(6) Improvement of transmission and distribution grid capacity must align with generation expansion to facilitate smooth integration of the expanding variable energy resources like solar and wind into the grid.		
Optimal planning of energy and water systems of a small island with a hourly OSeMOSYS model	Island of Favignana (Italy)	Case study	The research studies the water-energy nexus on a small island, examining various conditions: (1) Evaluating the benefits and trade-offs of different time resolutions in the analysis of reverse osmosis desalination for islands. (2) Assessing the impact of incorporating emissions from maritime transport of water and diesel in the optimal solution. (3) Investigating the effects of emission limits and taxes on the optimal energy-water system	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 8760 timeslices (hourly resolution) Modelling horizon: 2020-2050	1 region	(1) Determining an appropriate time resolution is crucial, as varying time steps can significantly impact results in terms of overall investment and capacity expansion. (2) Considering emissions associated with maritime transport of diesel and water is relevant for comprehensive analysis. (3) Implementing a carbon tax, starting at 50 euros per ton of CO2 in 2020 and escalating to 140 euros per ton of CO2 by 2050, facilitates the achievement of a fully decarbonized energy-water system and results in the lowest cumulative emissions. This approach proves more effective than imposing annual limits on emissions.	(1) Increase the complexity of technological detail and extend the analysis to validate the methodology. (2) Analyse the impact of various carbon taxes on the island's energy transition. (3) Investigate the role of additional technologies for renewable generation storage, and water desalination.	[20]
Applying the open-source climate, land, energy, and water systems (CLEWs) model to Canada	Canada	Case study - Methodology	This paper examines the interactions within the Climate, Land, Energy, and Water system (CLEWs) concerning biofuels production and highlights the water and land system challenges associated with biofuels in Canada	Not applicable	Not applicable	Supplementary material available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 8 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2020-2050	8 regions	(1) Switchgrass biofuels have the potential to contribute to the decarbonization of the electricity system by serving as a low-carbon baseload generation option. (2) Among biofuel crops, those that can be cultivated on land not currently utilized or highly valued for other purposes may present fewer land use trade-offs. (3) In the context of Canada, the primary limitation of biofuels is	(1) Expanding the model to incorporate additional biofuel alternatives by encompassing a wider range of crops and biofuel production pathways. (2) Integrating more end-use energy sectors, particularly transportation. (3) Implementing operational steps to facilitate the development of a Climate, Land, Energy, and Water system (CLEWs) model for any country, streamlining the process.	[58]

									likely to be water use rather than land use. (4) The impacts on crop yields resulting from restricted water capacity and expanded land area are particularly significant considerations, especially as climate change increasingly affects crop production and water availability. (5) Biofuels might be better suited for application in hard-to-decarbonize sectors such as transportation and industry before being utilized for electricity generation.		
OSeMOSYS Global, an open-source, open data global electricity system model generator	Not applicable	Modelling	This paper introduces OSeMOSYS Global, an open-source and open-data model generator accessible to all, designed for the rapid and efficient creation of interconnected or standalone electricity system models. These models are geographically diverse and allow for the exploration of trade-offs and synergies associated with the large-scale deployment of renewable energy and expanded transmission capacity across extensive geographic regions.	A workflow management system that performs a sequence of Python scripts and terminal commands in a predefined order to generate, solve, and visualize the results from an OSeMOSYS model.	Code is available at [link]	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: Up to 288 timeslices Maximum modelling horizon: 2015-2100	Up to 265 nodes (global coverage)	Not applicable	(1) Integrating natural resource potentials for both biomass and geothermal sources into the model. (2) Utilizing weather models to generate capacity factors for wind, solar, and hydroelectric profiles, considering varying climate scenarios across different model horizons. (3) Including short-term and long-term storage options to enhance the assessment of integrating variable energy sources and accounting for seasonal effects. (4) Offering users options to select different time slicing approaches, such as representative days or clustering methods, to validate temporal assumptions and accurately represent time-dependent input data. (5) Enhancing demand projections to accommodate increased electrification in the coming decades as decarbonization policies become more stringent.	[106]

										<p>(6) Expanding OSeMOSYS Global to include other energy sectors beyond electricity, transforming it into a comprehensive energy system model.</p> <p>(7) Developing a CLEWs Global workflow on top of the OSeMOSYS Global workflow to broaden the scope of research questions the model generator can address.</p> <p>(8) Linking OSeMOSYS Global with a more detailed power system model can provide valuable insights into the operational feasibility of the results.</p>	
Potential clean energy transition pathways in the US Virgin Islands using carbon sensitive policy options	U.S Virgin Islands (Unite States)	Case study	This study applies a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches to evaluate a range of measures and future scenarios, offering insights for policymakers on sustainable development for the islands. It uses stakeholder-driven modeling to formulate energy scenarios, while LEAP-OSeMOSYS is employed to determine the optimal capacity expansion plan aligned with these scenarios. Additionally, the analysis includes considerations of the impacts on electricity demand resulting from extreme weather events and the integration of electric vehicles into the grid.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 12 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2021-2050	2 regions	<p>(1) Wind and commercial solar should be given priority in capacity expansion efforts, while off-grid solar necessitates policy interventions to lower costs and stimulate demand.</p> <p>(2) To effectively decarbonize the transportation sector and reduce gasoline and diesel consumption, deploying electric vehicles (EVs) alone may not suffice to achieve significant reductions in transportation fuel usage. This will necessitate a combination of additional initiatives, such as promoting the shift to public transportation and enhancing the efficiency of internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles, among others. However, the potential revenue from charging taxes on EVs might outweigh the losses from fuel taxes.</p>	<p>(1) Considering the decarbonization of the transport sector as a whole, encompassing sea transport in addition to land transport.</p> <p>(2) Conducting a deeper analysis of short and medium-term perspectives. This can aid in better planning for the decarbonization efforts.</p> <p>(3) Shifting focus from examining policy packages to analyzing the effects of specific individual policies as scenarios. This approach can provide a clearer understanding of the impacts and outcomes of each policy upon implementation.</p> <p>(4) Conducting high-resolution resource assessments to demonstrate the wind and solar resources available and attract commercial interests. This includes studies assessing wind potential in accessible mountainous regions and conducting techno-economic assessments of different types of wind</p>	[83]

										turbines and solar photovoltaic (PV) systems.	
Strategic low-cost energy investment opportunities and challenges towards achieving universal electricity access (SDG7) in forty-eight African nations	Africa	Case study - Methodology	This study presents an electrification least-cost investment outlook for Africa on a continental, regional, and national scale, leveraging energy systems analysis enhanced with geospatial data. The approach enables the identification of energy pathways while considering the nation's priorities in achieving universal access to electricity, allocating power generation investments spatially, assessing financial capacity and technological maturity, and accounting for environmental and policy constraints alongside energy demand growth across various sectors. Additionally, the analysis evaluates the success rates of Sustainable Development Goal 7 (SDG7) and its sub-targets in each country. Lastly, the study discusses the socio-economic benefits, particularly job creation, associated with these energy transitions.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Supplementary data available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: Not indicated Modelling horizon: 2015-2030	48 regions	(1) The trajectory of renewable technology costs is pivotal for achieving Sustainable Development Goal 7 (SDG7) in Africa. (2) Off-grid and hybrid mini-grid solar technologies are anticipated to play a significant role in electrifying residential areas. (3) Natural gas dominates fossil fuel installed capacity across all scenarios. Conversely, hydropower is the predominant renewable source. It will continue to be so by 2030 unless the costs of solar technologies experience significant decreases in the coming decade. (4) A higher proportion of renewable energy sources in the energy mix diminishes reliance on imported fuels, fosters local job creation, and enhances cost efficiency.	(1) Enhance the sub-annual time resolution to effectively capture the variability in electricity generated by renewable technologies. (2) Incorporate country-specific hydro capacity factors and individually represent hydropower plants rather than aggregating them based on size. (3) Improve the representation of national energy systems by explicitly including a representation of reserve margin in each country's power system. (4) Explicitly model storage technologies to accurately account for their impact on energy systems. (5) Disaggregate final energy demand across sectors and incorporate exogenous assumptions regarding fuel switching and efficiency improvements. (6) Include analysis of oil and coal exports to provide a comprehensive understanding of energy dynamics.	[123]
Energy efficiency and conservation values in a variable renewable electricity system	Mauritius	Case study	This study presents an empirical model of a renewable electricity system to quantify the efficiency and conservation measures in terms of dollars per kilowatt-hour (kWh) saved.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 730 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2040	1 region	The marginal benefits of energy efficiency surpass the average costs of electricity, while the value of energy conservation during times of limited electricity supply can exceed double the average cost of electricity production. This underscores the importance of promoting efficiency and conservation measures within a high variable renewable energy system. Economic tools such as dynamic pricing, discounts, and subsidies	(1) Enhance the methodology to distinguish between efficiency measures and conservation measures. (2) Develop a method to estimate the costs associated with both efficiency and conservation measures. (3) Incorporate modelling for short-term storage to enhance the representation of energy storage solutions. (4) Broaden the scope of energy sector modelling to achieve an integrated energy model, encompassing multiple	[163]

									can effectively incentivize energy management. However, careful consideration of social aspects is crucial to prevent adverse effects on the most vulnerable individuals when designing electricity pricing policies.	energy sources and sectors to provide a comprehensive understanding of the energy system.	
Assessing flexibility for integrating renewable energies into carbon neutral multi-regional systems: The case of the Chilean power system	Chile	Modelling	The study introduces the development of a methodological framework that applies a customized adaptation of OSeMOSYS to analyze the role of concentrated solar power with thermal energy storage (CSP-TES), battery energy storage systems (BESS), and transmission expansion. This framework aims to facilitate the transition towards more renewable systems capable of ensuring the necessary flexibility in the power supply.	A proxy of the underlying Unit Commitment problem, enabling the modelling of ramp-rates, start-up rates, minimum stable operation levels, ramp costs, and additional fuel consumption levels based on Gardumi et al. (2019) and Welsh et al. (2015). Additional constraints to represent the proportions between the total capacities of two components in a technology setting, such as CSP-TES and BESS plants. A constraint to represent the maximum average activity that a technology can experience within a season of the year, as seen in the case of hydropower units.	Mathematical modelling is available with subscription to Elsevier Code version: MathProg	Available with subscription to Elsevier [link]	Intrayear resolution: 96 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2018-2050	4 regions	(1) The flexibility requirements of the system operating with high levels of variable renewable generation can be met through various means: dispatchable generation from CSP-TES, hydro dam plants, and natural gas plants; enhanced transmission capacity and hourly activity of transmission lines, particularly in areas with high renewable potentials and consumption; storage, combining capacity from battery energy storage systems (BESS) and pumped-storage hydropower; and energy curtailment if necessary. (2) A coordinated operation between CSP-TES and photovoltaic plants necessitates a CSP-TES configuration capable of providing flexibility, requiring lower values of the solar multiple factor compared to those needed for supplying base load. (3) Incentives for investing in BESS can promote the growth of photovoltaic capacity in the system while potentially reducing CSP-TES capacity, thereby maintaining renewable penetration levels. Alternatively, incentives for investing in CSP-TES could sustain	(1) Integrate the inherent uncertainty of renewable generation profiles into our analysis. (2) Expand our tool to assess scenarios involving the use of hydrogen as an energy vector for flexibility. This expansion entails addressing additional curtailment utilization, energy storage strategies, and electrolytic production under flexible demand response strategies.	[139]

									photovoltaic generation levels but might reduce wind and natural gas generation.		
Planning the decarbonisation of energy systems: The importance of applying time series clustering to long-term models	Pantelleria island (Italy)	Modelling	This study aims to fill the gap in long-term energy modelling frameworks by addressing the representation of variability in variable renewable energy sources (VRES) and the simulation of storage technologies. A novel methodology utilizing interconnected clustered representative days (RDs) has been integrated into OSeMOSYS. This approach is then applied to a reference case study featuring high penetration levels of renewable energy sources (RES) along with energy storage technologies. The resulting outcomes are compared with those derived from a traditional method to illustrate the advantages of implementing interconnected clustered RDs in identifying the optimal decarbonization pathway.	A clustering method is initially introduced to define representative days based on attributes such as the time series of specific fuel demands and productivity from renewable technologies. Additional sets, parameters, variables, and equations are incorporated to implement clustered interconnected representative days while preserving their chronological order. Furthermore, new components are integrated to enhance the modelling of storage based on the revised time representation structure.	Available at [link] Code version: Pyomo	The data for the case study is available in the same article	Intrayear resolution: Sensitivity analysis from 30 to 1865 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2021-2040	1 region	Enhancements in time representation would improve the accuracy of sizing variable renewable energy (VRE) technologies and storage units. Early sizing facilitates the implementation of energy planning policies and enables effective targeting of public and private investments.	(1) Investigate the applicability of the introduced method to complex energy systems, where computational burden could pose a significant obstacle. (2) Explore the suitability of the novel approach for analyzing the role of various storage methods, such as hydrogen. (3) Analyze the effectiveness of different clustering algorithms to identify the most suitable ones for time series clustering.	[138]
Climate, Land, Energy and Water systems interactions-From key concepts to model implementation with OSeMOSYS	Not applicable	Methodology	This paper outlines the process of conducting a quantitative analysis of Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems (CLEWs) using OSeMOSYS. It provides a step-by-step guide on how to represent climate, land, energy, and water systems within OSeMOSYS, accompanied by an interpretation of sets, parameters, and variables in the OSeMOSYS code. Through a hypothetical	Not applicable	Not applicable	Supplementary data available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 8 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2020-2050	1 region	Academics, researchers, government officials, institutional actors, and all involved with the Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems (CLEWs) approach, as well as the Nexus concept in general, will find this paper invaluable for initiating discussions and dialogues on the Nexus. The presented use cases can aid in designing analyses similar to	Not indicated	[132]

			<p>case study, the paper demonstrates the development of a CLEWs model in OSeMOSYS. System-centered scenario analysis is conducted using the integrated model example to illustrate its practical application. The analysis of results showcases how integrated insights, including conflicts, trade-offs, opportunities, and synergies, can be derived from the quantitative exercise. Furthermore, the paper explores the use of the OSeMOSYS-CLEWs example in teaching, training, and open science to facilitate knowledge transfer and advancement in the field.</p>						<p>CLEWs, offering a broader perspective for coordinated planning activities related to Nexus assessments or the development of research plans.</p>		
<p>An Energy Cost Assessment of Future Energy Scenarios: A Case Study on San Pietro Island</p>	<p>San Pietro Island (Italy)</p>	<p>Case study - Methodology</p>	<p>This study seeks to enhance the functionality of the well-established long-term energy model framework, "OSeMOSYS," by introducing an additional tool capable of estimating various types of Levelized Cost Of Electricity (LCOE): including real and theoretical LCOE for each technology, as well as real and theoretical system LCOE. Addressing a common gap in existing modelling frameworks, this tool provides valuable insights into energy costs, aiding policymakers in decision-making processes.</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>Not available</p>	<p>Intrayear resolution: 96 timeslices</p> <p>Modelling horizon: 2020-2050</p>	<p>1 region</p>	<p>(1) The installation of mature Renewable Energy Sources (RES) power plants such as photovoltaic (PV) and wind turbines can already reduce electricity generation costs in the short term. (2) Wind energy plays a crucial role in the initial phase of the transition. Governments should facilitate the installation of onshore or offshore wind turbines, especially if ambitious decarbonization targets are being pursued. (3) To maintain grid stability, the penetration of Variable Renewable Energy Sources (VRES) in the power mix should not exceed 80%. Investments in grid reinforcement and balancing are necessary regardless, especially in anticipation of further electrification of the transport sector.</p>	<p>(1) Implement time series clustering to derive representative typical periods, without averaging starting values, can enhance the robustness of results and improve storage sizing accuracy. (2) Create a short-term energy model specific to the electric system, which can be integrated with the estimation of Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE), would provide a more comprehensive assessment of the costs associated with sustainable scenarios featuring a high proportion of Variable Renewable Energy Sources (VRESs)</p>	<p>[21]</p>

									(4) Various storage options, including Li-ion batteries, flow batteries, and hydrogen, should be explored to identify the most suitable solution from both technical and economic perspectives. Due to grid interconnection with the mainland, the presence of a storage facility may be less prominent, at least initially in the transition phase.		
Modeling of the dominican republic energy systems with OSeMOSYS to assess alternative scenarios for the expansion of renewable energy sources	Dominican Republic	Case study	This article aims to enhance comprehension of alternative scenarios for expanding renewable energy sources in the Dominican Republic's (DR) energy mix. The insights derived from this analysis are valuable for decision-makers in the DR and other nations sharing similar traits, such as susceptibility to climate change-related impacts and heavy reliance on imported fossil fuels.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 12 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2022-2040	1 region	(1) The results obtained validate the findings of the "Investment Planning in Electricity Generation of the Dominican Republic 2040" published by the Ministry of Energy and Mines regarding the necessity of constructing new power plants. (2) Despite the reduction in CO2 emissions observed during the evaluated time frame, the anticipated increase in demand requires the expansion of generation capacity based on thermal power plants starting from 2032. (3) While solar PV technology boasts lower costs compared to wind and biomass, the intermittency of solar resources at night makes wind and biomass technologies more competitive. As a result, the model suggests prioritizing the expansion of generation capacity from wind and biomass technologies.	Model scenarios incorporating storage systems to enhance the dispatch capacity of renewable energy sources (RES) in the analysis	[72]
Between path dependencies and renewable energy potentials: A case study of the Egyptian power system	Egypt	Modelling	The paper explores potential pathways for the domestic power system in Egypt, emphasizing regional deployment and its implications for the	Investment periods are modelled in five-year time steps.	Code implementation is available at [link]	Supplementary data available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 144 timeslices	8 regions	(1) Wind and PV installations emerge as cost-competitive options capable of meeting a significant portion of projected demand	(1) Enhance the model with a detailed representation of the power transmission network and its expansion plans.	[60]

			<p>transmission network. It assesses renewable energy potentials at 320 sites across eight sub-regions, offering insights into the spatial allocation of future power plants and associated requirements for regional network interconnection capacity expansion.</p>	<p>Constraints are applied to model CSP storage, ensuring that it must be emptied at the end of each representative day type, such as the transition from a workday to a weekend day or vice versa, thereby eliminating the need to balance the storage level over the entire modelling period.</p> <p>Constraints are included to enforce exogenously determined minimum shares of RES capacity.</p>			Modelling horizon: 2017-2042		<p>growth. Wind power deployment should span across the country, while PV installations are suggested closer to load centers in the northern region to minimize transmission line extensions. This approach optimizes resource utilization despite less favorable potentials in the North. (2) The addition of coal-fired power plants lacks economic justification, and solar thermal power plants are deemed unviable under current model conditions. However, tailored subsidies could make solar thermal plants viable contributors to decarbonization efforts, given their flexibility in substituting for inefficient fossil-fuel technologies during peak demand. (3) A cautious approach to renewable energy expansion, as targeted by the government, is found to be more costly compared to a more aggressive deployment pathway.</p>	<p>(2) Assess supply security by investigating inflexibilities in the power system and analyzing the impacts of uncertainties, particularly in relation to increased penetration of renewable energy sources. (3) Integrate normative climate policy scenarios to examine the emissions behavior and their alignment with climate targets and objective</p>	
The effects of climate change mitigation strategies on the energy system of Africa and its associated water footprint	Africa	Case study	<p>This study provides a quantitative multi-annual analysis, estimating energy requirements, water withdrawal (WW), consumption, carbon dioxide emissions, and the costs of meeting future energy system needs in Africa, while also considering trade links among African nations. By conducting a continental-scale analysis, the study captures the disparities in energy and water resources between nations, as well as</p>	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	<p>Intrayear resolution: Not indicated</p> <p>Modelling horizon: 2015-2065</p>	48 regions	<p>(1) Meeting the 1.5°C pathway in Africa necessitates higher water withdrawal (WW) levels overall and per unit of final energy, underscoring the critical importance of proper water resource management. (2) Energy trade plays a crucial role, with cooperation between neighbouring countries offering the potential to reduce overall costs and greenhouse gas emissions at the whole-Africa level. The East</p>	<p>(1) Incorporating agricultural and municipal water withdrawals for each African nation alongside our results could reveal the impact of scenarios on water-stress levels. (2) Hydrological modelling of planned dams would offer more precise quantification of dam productivity and impacts. (3) Broader social and environmental effects of hydropower and nuclear should be further explored at a power pool or regional scale, along with mitigation</p>	[96]

			resulting energy trade flows.						<p>Africa Power Pool (EAPP) emerges as a significant net exporter of electricity due to its high renewable potential.</p> <p>(3) The integrated model highlights the interconnected nature of energy and water security. As nations invest in new power plants to bolster electricity exports, this could strain available water resources and potentially lead to increased geopolitical tensions.</p> <p>(4) Countries with significant energy export potential, such as Algeria, Nigeria, and South Africa, must carefully consider the trade-offs between energy exports, local consumption for economic growth, and increased water requirements. Moreover, countries planning coastal thermal generation capacity, like Egypt, Algeria, Morocco, South Africa, and Angola, should factor in climate change risks, such as sea-level rise, given their reliance on seawater for cooling.</p>	<p>strategies, to better understand the implications of these technologies.</p> <p>(4) Modelling storage technologies can enhance the analysis of future energy scenarios.</p> <p>(5) Improved data, such as country-specific information on future power plant investments and cooling types, coupled with spatial techniques like a soft-link with a geographic information system (GIS), could facilitate the identification and allocation of different cooling technologies to future thermal power plants.</p> <p>(6) Linking a spatial database of power plants with precipitation patterns and cooling technologies would enhance the estimation of water factors.</p> <p>(7) Incorporating country-specific reserve margins, rather than using averages, would enhance the accuracy of power sector projections and improve the representation of national energy systems.</p> <p>(8) Accounting for the costs of energy efficiency measures and the reduction in energy service provision in an endogenous manner.</p>	
Selected 'Starter kit' energy system modelling data for selected countries in Africa, East Asia, and South America (#CCG, 2021)	Included countries in Africa, South America, and Asia.	Data article	This article offers valuable data that serves as a foundation for constructing basic zero-order energy system models tailored to developing countries in Africa, East Asia, and South America. The provided dataset comprises essential parameters such as costs, operational lifespan, efficiency, installed capacity, capacity factors, and emission	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Timeseries data: 2015 - 2070	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	[164]

			factors, among others. This comprehensive dataset enables researchers and policymakers to initiate energy system modelling endeavours and conduct scenario analyses.								
The role of US-Canada electricity trade in North American decarbonization pathways	US-Canada	Modelling	This paper investigates the dynamics of U.S.-Canada electricity generation and trade, particularly in the context of driving decarbonization efforts within the integrated system. Building upon existing research, this study introduces spatial regionalization of both countries, leveraging North American Electric Reliability Corporation (NERC) data for enhanced granularity. Furthermore, it employs a more detailed temporal resolution and analyses variations in transmission investment costs, shedding light on key factors influencing the transition towards a low-carbon energy landscape.	The reserve margin constraint was modified. Authors enhance its applicability by allowing it to be implemented for each region individually. This adjustment involves modifying the formulation to index over the regionally defined fuels instead of summing them to a global reserve margin. Consequently, we can now apply reserve margin values to various fuels within the same region and implement region-specific reserve margins,	Code implementation is available in the appendix [link]	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 96 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2019-2050	18 regions	(1) Achieving net-zero emissions requires scaling up hydro and renewable energy sources to generate emission-free electricity. In our model, this involves expanding hydroelectric capacity in Canada for scenarios with abundant hydro resources, while both Canada and the U.S. augment hydro, wind, and solar capacities in scenarios with limited hydro potential. Additionally, gas-fired power plays a crucial role across all scenarios, providing flexible generation to ensure cost-effective compliance with reserve margin requirements. (2) The balance of electricity trade is highly sensitive to greenhouse gas (GHG) targets, indicating that even minor policy disparities across jurisdictions can significantly influence trade dynamics. Taking early action becomes crucial in this context. (3) Minor adjustments in transmission costs have limited impact on overall system investments, with transmission expansion being primarily driven by climate policies and resultant changes in generation portfolios rather than the upfront capital costs. Therefore, the focus should be on determining the optimal	(1) The inclusion of short-term energy storage like batteries or long-term options such as power-to-gas for hydrogen production can offer insights into their impact on generation and capacity mixes. (2) Implementing region-specific cost multipliers for transmission line capital costs, tailored to address geographic barriers like mountains, can refine the accuracy of transmission capacity expansion assessments. (3) Encompassing Mexico in the analysis and calculating optimal electricity generation and transmission investments across all North American countries.	[36]

									generation mix for the integrated system, with transmission infrastructure development aligning with emerging generation strategies.		
Assessment of Impacts of Climate Change on Hydropower-Dominated Power System-The Case of Ethiopia	Ethiopia	Case study	This article explores the effects of climate change, particularly severe drought, on hydropower generation and the environment in Ethiopia. Using the OSeMOSYS energy system modelling tool, the study compares two scenarios: the Drought Scenario, where reservoir capacity is halved due to drought, and the New Policy Scenario. The aim is to understand how electricity generation and CO2 emissions would be impacted in the future under drought conditions. By characterizing the Drought Scenario, the research aims to provide insights for decision-makers in planning future renewable power systems, including the need for backup solutions.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 8 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2065	1 region	(1) The drought phenomenon significantly affects renewable energy technologies, leading to a premature peak in electricity production from hydro power plants and a greater deployment of solar power technologies. (2) Despite a substantial increase in electricity production from Solar PV, CSP, nuclear, and biomass, the supply will not meet the demand without reinforcement from fossil fuels. (3) Climate-driven losses in hydropower must be offset by the introduction of new infrastructures, which could provide enough power to ensure the future stability of the Ethiopian electric system.	(1) Assess the potential impacts of climate change on additional components of the power sector, including wind and solar resources. (2) Investigate the tradeoffs and synergies among different expansion pathways in the Ethiopian power sector, considering their potential impacts on other sectors such as water and land.	[25]
Supporting Decarbonization Strategies of Local Energy Systems by De-Risking Investments in Renewables: A Case Study on Pantelleria Island	Pantelleria Island (Italy)	Modelling	The primary aim of this paper is to highlight the importance of identifying priority energy policy measures at the local level, particularly considering uncertainties surrounding community engagement in the decarbonization process. To bolster policymakers' efforts in achieving high self-sufficiency targets for local energy systems, the paper introduces an energy scenario analysis based on a modified OSeMOSYS framework. Key innovations include: (1) Introducing a new module in the OSeMOSYS framework to address the	New dispatchable generation module which establishes the minimum fuel level supplied by dispatchable technologies during each time-slice. It incorporates new parameters, variables, and constraints.	Code implementation is available at [link] Code version: Pyomo	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 50 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2020-2050	1 region	(1) The widespread adoption of distributed PV + storage systems is pivotal for reaching ambitious decarbonization goals, as it offers a cost-effective solution supported by technology learning curves. Conversely, the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) entails significant capital costs and requires larger overall installed capacity. (2) The optimal configuration of the energy system is heavily influenced by the technical potentials available for the system under examination. It's	(1) Expand on the proposed approach to consider additional factors related to citizen engagement in shaping energy systems. Specifically, the role of building occupants and the potential for energy savings should be examined, given their significant impact on residential and tertiary sector energy consumption. (2) Explore solutions for effectively managing the sizing of storage facilities, especially when modelling high shares of variable renewable energy sources (V-RES). This may involve implementing clustering algorithms on input time-series data.	[95]

			requirement for dispatchable generation in energy islands. (2) Proposing a scenario analysis approach to mitigate unpredictability in community engagement and prioritize the implementation of new renewable energy power plants.						crucial for decision-makers to carefully consider environmental and landscape constraints, as well as the needs of local communities when addressing this aspect.		
Optimizing renewable-based energy supply options for power generation in Ethiopia	Ethiopia	Case study	The study applies OSeMOSYS in conjunction with the national development plan (HERA) to outline the most cost-effective energy supply options. These options are aimed at achieving national objectives, such as transitioning to a lower-middle-income status by 2030 and further advancing to medium and higher middle-income statuses by 2040 and 2050, respectively.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 6 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2020-2050	1 region	(1) Ethiopia's renewable energy potential appears sufficient to align with the national plan's objectives, aiming to raise grid connections to 96% by 2030. (2) Achieving the target of 100% access rate and middle-income country status from the current low access rate entails a significant surge in total investment costs compared to a business-as-usual (BAU) scenario. (3) As hydropower and geothermal resources approach their maximum exploitable limits, solar and wind technologies are anticipated to play pivotal roles in Ethiopia's ambitious electrification pathways.	(1) Incorporate the modelling of the transport sector to account for the required transformation in terms of reducing imported fuels and associated emissions. (2) Enhance the quality of the technology efficiency data and make corresponding adjustments to the model.	[48]
A scenario analysis of potential long-term impacts of COVID-19 on the Tunisian electricity sector	Tunisia	Case study	The study analyzes the potential long-term ramifications of the COVID-19 pandemic in Tunisia using an energy-economy model. It offers insights into three primary areas: (1) The potential shifts in the cost-competitiveness of various technological solutions aimed at meeting future electricity demand. This analysis considers changes in demand patterns, international fuel prices influenced by the pandemic, and potential shifts in policy and investment priorities.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Supplementary data available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 108 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2040	1 region	(1) All examined trajectories for expanding Tunisia's electricity system surpass the targets outlined in the Tunisian Solar Plan for installed renewable capacity. (2) In most scenarios, CO2 emissions from the electricity sector are projected to increase by 2040 compared to 2020, hindering Tunisia's progress towards deep decarbonization. This poses a risk of economic repercussions if the EU introduces a Carbon	(1) Updating assumptions using available datasets and open-source model infrastructure, along with integrating technology learning methods from existing literature. (2) Re-evaluating the potential of biomass in the electricity mix and improving the database for batteries and other storage solutions. (3) Detailed ad-hoc studies to estimate the economic assumptions such as average wages, wage share of value added and local content	[29]

			<p>(2) The trajectory of Tunisia's electricity sector in the post-pandemic era concerning its journey towards decarbonization.</p> <p>(3) The implications of different investment decisions in the electricity supply sector on job creation and loss across the broader Tunisian economy.</p>						<p>Border Adjustment Mechanism for electricity imports.</p> <p>(3) Solar photovoltaic power emerges as a highly competitive solution, unaffected significantly by sharp decreases in gas prices linked to the COVID-19 pandemic.</p> <p>(4) A significant reliance on gas-fired generation exposes Tunisia to the volatile nature of gas prices, as observed in recent years.</p> <p>(5) Investments in renewables and energy efficiency measures contribute substantially to job creation, with the level dependent on the local content of the investments. This makes a robust expansion of renewable energies and energy efficiency measures potentially attractive for green recovery stimulus packages.</p> <p>(6) Prioritizing local production and construction of renewable technologies aligns with decarbonization goals while promoting job creation. Solar PV, in particular, stands out as a cost-competitive solution under assumed costs.</p> <p>(7) Directives promoting energy efficiency measures, along with tailored programs and incentives for end-users, could be crucial for effective implementation and adoption.</p>		
A clustering approach to improve spatial representation in	Vietnam	Methodology	This paper introduces a modelling framework aimed at addressing key gaps observed in existing Water-	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 6 timeslices	3 regions	(1) Crop migration in Vietnam is proposed as a strategy to increase productivity and mitigate	(1) Incorporate seasonal variations in crop yields and multi-cropping techniques.	[93]

water-energy-food models			<p>Energy-Food (WEF) models. It illustrates the framework's application in quantifying the interconnections between water, energy, and food sectors in Vietnam. The modelling framework boasts the following characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It adopts a fully integrated approach, simultaneously and equally considering the WEF sectors. - Spatial considerations of WEF resources and trade-offs are incorporated, albeit with manageable computational complexities. - The framework is designed to be flexible, scalable, and accessible, enabling reproducible nexus assessments across various scales, geographies, and political contexts using open-source code and data. 				Modelling horizon: 2016-2030		<p>adverse effects of land use change.</p> <p>(2) The energy generation mix in Vietnam is expected to shift from a balanced distribution among natural gas, hydro, and coal to one dominated by natural gas.</p> <p>(3) The agricultural sector is projected to expand significantly to accommodate a growing population and meet Vietnam's ambitious crop export goals.</p> <p>(4) While the total water demand projected in the model can be satisfied by Vietnam's renewable water resources, further analysis is needed to assess the spatial distribution of demands and resources to ensure sustainable water management.</p>	<p>(2) Evaluate the environmental effects of agricultural inputs such as fertilizers.</p> <p>(3) Analyze soil carbon dynamics related to changes in land use.</p>	
The open source electricity Model Base for Europe-An engagement framework for open and transparent European energy modelling	Europe	Case study	<p>This paper introduces OSeMBE (Open Source electricity Model Base for Europe), a fully open-source and user-friendly long-term energy planning model designed to offer insights into Europe's transition to a low-carbon power system. Unlike traditional energy system models, OSeMBE is not meant to be complex but rather serves as an engagement tool. It aims to bridge the gap between non-modelers, students, and the energy modeling community, making modeling science more accessible. The paper provides a detailed overview of OSeMBE's creation and structure,</p>	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	<p>Intrayear resolution: 15 timeslices</p> <p>Modelling horizon: 2015-2050</p>	30 regions	Not applicable	<p>Broaden the model's scope by incorporating additional sectors such as heating and cooling. This expansion would enable the representation of the effects of growing electrification across various sectors and facilitate the inclusion of flexibility options needed to integrate a high proportion of variable renewable energies.</p>	[35]

			laying the foundation for its accessibility and usability.								
Modelling least cost electricity system scenarios for Bangladesh using OSeMOSYS	Bangladesh	Case study	The paper contributes to discussions regarding Bangladesh's electricity sector by offering an entirely open-source model infrastructure and conducting an extensive analysis using open data and diverse scenarios. These scenarios explore various narratives, incorporating assumptions about technological advancements, renewable energy potential, fuel expenses, and policy changes. The insights derived from these scenarios revolve around two main themes: - Assessing the potential and cost-effectiveness of low-carbon electricity compared to expanding fossil fuel-based capacity. - Evaluating the trade-offs associated with different fossil fuel supply alternatives.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Supplementary data available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 10 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2019-2045	1 region	(1) Utility-scale solar PV emerges as economically competitive in all scenarios, highlighting the need for further research into its actual potential. (2) Ultra-supercritical coal power remains the primary electricity source in 2045 across scenarios, except under stringent emissions regulations, a carbon tax, or falling LNG prices. (3) Apart from solar expansion, significant emission reductions can be achieved by increasing nuclear power, boosting imports, and substituting USPC with natural gas CC. While the first two options are economically viable in most cases, the third option depends on emission regulations, carbon taxation, or LNG price reductions.	(1) Explore the impact of additional uncertainties such as the dynamic price changes over time. (2) Incorporate the analysis of infrastructure costs, including regasification infrastructure for LNG and expansion of the transmission and distribution grid. (3) Conduct spatially-detailed analyses to assess wind power potential using location-specific data on wind capacity factors. (4) Integrate price elasticity and land use requirements into the modelling process to capture their effects accurately.	[32]
Potential Climate Change Risks to Meeting Zimbabwe's NDC Goals and How to Become Resilient	Zimbabwe	Case study	This paper aims to assess the vulnerability of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) to climate change risks and to propose strategies to enhance their resilience, thereby ensuring the achievement of emissions targets.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 24 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2010-2050	1 region	(1) Implement a roadmap with clear milestones for the adoption of clean adaptation policies and measures (PAMs) to effectively address climate challenges. (2) Harmonize hydropower planning with water and agriculture policies across sectors to ensure efficient and sustainable water resource management. (3) Revise regulatory frameworks and market rules governing the power sector, coal purchases, and energy efficiency markets to facilitate the transition to cleaner energy sources and practices.	(1) Conduct a thorough assessment of a wide range of scenarios to provide a comprehensive understanding of vulnerability, resilience, and adaptivity of the country's NDCs. (2) Integrate assessments of water use and constraints across different scenarios to understand water availability for hydropower generation and balancing. (3) Consider regional integration, including water basins and power markets, to provide a more holistic analysis. (4) Include detailed assessments of energy efficiency policies and measures, operational	[156]

										regimes for restructuring conventional power generation, and the costs and performance changes associated with this transition. (5) Evaluate ecosystem and institutional requirements to develop action pathways with clear milestones for various stakeholders to achieve.	
Three stages in the co-transformation of the energy and mobility sectors	Germany	Case study	The aim of this study is to analyze the optimal evolution and functioning of Germany's energy system, with a special emphasis on electromobility and sector coupling. Firstly, the research examines the cost-effective deployment of renewable energy capacities, storage systems, and power-to-mobility (PtM) installations needed to achieve predetermined emission reduction goals. It delineates various stages of the energy transition marked by significant expansions in different technologies. Secondly, the study delves into the operational dynamics of these technologies, focusing on system flexibility. It identifies which technologies contribute to flexibility during different stages of the transition and provides a detailed examination of PtM operation.	Not applicable	Not applicable	The data for the case study is available in the same article but it requires subscription to Elsevier [link]	Intrayear resolution: 288 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2018-2050	1 region	(1) A substantial reduction in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, approximately 75% lower than 1990 levels by 2040, is feasible without significant systemic changes. Achieving this reduction relies on expanding renewable power generation, particularly solar photovoltaic (PV), transitioning from coal to gas-fired power plants, and increasing battery storage capacities. These measures can be implemented using mature technologies. (2) Solar PV is prioritized over wind power, even in Germany with its relatively limited solar resources. By 2030, PV capacities nearly triple while minimal additional wind capacity is added. This strategic emphasis on PV could help alleviate the challenge of public acceptance for new onshore wind turbines, a notable obstacle in Germany's energy transition. (3) Beyond 2040, the energy transformation encounters substantial challenges as emissions caps become more stringent. Power-to-Mobility (PtM) technology	(1) Incorporate the heating sector into the model to assess its potential role in sector coupling. (2) Explore spatial aspects, including exports and imports, to better understand how energy flows between regions and countries. (3) Conduct further analysis on the cost progression of solar PV technologies. (4) Expand the product portfolio to include other renewable energy carriers such as hydrogen, methanol, dimethyl ether, etc.	[56]

									evolves from a consumer to a provider of flexibility, adapting to variable renewable generation and load fluctuations. PtM's role shifts to balancing the evening peak demand, driven by the charging of battery electric vehicles (BEVs), and synchronizing with the needs of both the electricity and mobility sectors.		
The Global Least-cost user-friendly CLEWs Open-Source Exploratory model	Not applicable	Modelling	The paper introduces the Global Least-cost User-friendly CLEWs Open-Source Exploratory (GLUCOSE) model, which serves as a global Integrated Assessment Model (IAM). Built on the OSeMOSYS tool and the CLEWs framework, GLUCOSE offers an accessible and open-source platform for exploring policy measures and their potential impacts on integrated resource systems worldwide. Its simplified structure allows for efficient use of computational resources, enabling the generation of numerous scenarios or quick preliminary investigations. GLUCOSE is designed to be user-friendly, making it suitable for educational purposes and training for various stakeholders, including students, researchers, and decision-makers, aiming to facilitate discussions on sustainable global resource management.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 1 timeslice Modelling horizon: 2010-2050	1 region	Not applicable	(1) Enhance the materials module by incorporating additional technology and price options, enabling the model to select investments that combine various transformation technologies with different conversion efficiencies and emission factors. (2) Integrate a simplified representation of the global hydrological cycle to provide insights into water resource utilization and depletion over time, offering a more comprehensive understanding of water resources within the model. (3) Consider subdividing passenger transport and freight into short- and long-distance travel segments to better capture potential technology market penetration rates. This refinement would enable the model to simulate shifts toward public transport, such as railways, for long-distance passenger travel, as opposed to private transportation modes like roadways.	[155]
Integrating supply and demand-side management in renewable-based energy systems	Brazil	Modelling	The study covers the design of a co-optimization model for supply and demand coordination, resulting in a new integrated planning model, particularly effective for systems with a	The modified code includes DR strategies code based on Welsh (2013) and own enhancements to compute unmet	Not available	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 96 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2018-2040	4 regions	(1) In systems with a high share of hydropower, the potential for load shifting to balance the load is somewhat limited. However, there is significant potential for	(1) Investigating other balancing technologies, such as batteries and electric vehicles, to evaluate their technical and economic impacts on DR potential.	[140]

			high share of renewable energy sources (RES) under varying demand flexibility conditions. It also assesses the technical and economic impacts of demand response (DR) measures in such systems. Additionally, the study proposes a concept of "opportunity cost" for computing the price of unmet demand (load shedding), based on each region's spot price.	demand seasonally.					<p>demand response (DR) to reduce the need for additional thermal capacity, thereby lowering CO2 emissions and overall system costs.</p> <p>(2) DR evaluation can contribute to defining cost-effective demand-side management (DSM) portfolios tailored to specific customer classes and technologies. Given the country's size and diversity, these portfolios should be region-specific to address environmental objectives and economic development targets.</p> <p>(3) Integrating DR resources into the Brazilian electricity market will require regulatory changes. These changes could enhance the benefits of DR for nearly all stakeholders, fostering a more efficient and sustainable energy system.</p>	<p>(2) Splitting the country into individual processes or appliances to enhance model granularity and assess the technical and economic load flexibility for each process or appliance.</p> <p>(3) Conducting a holistic evaluation of demand-side management (DSM), integrating energy efficiency measures with DR strategies.</p> <p>(4) Assessing user acceptance issues, considering that social behavior significantly affects practical load management potential.</p> <p>(5) Determining the optimal future DR portfolio for the country.</p> <p>(6) Addressing the geographical distribution of DR participants to ensure comprehensive coverage and effectiveness.</p>	
Regional energy security goes South: Examining energy integration in South America	South America	Case study	The article exposes two contributions: 1) Proposal of regional integrations as a mechanism for ensuring countries' energy security, 2) A regional assessment of South America as a subregion in Latin America with its own particularities	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 48 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2013-2058	13 regions	<p>(1) Energy integration is essential for promoting regional energy security. It reduces the need for increased installed capacity and minimizes geographic and socio-environmental impacts.</p> <p>(2) Argentina and Bolivia play a central role in regional energy integration due to their borders with five countries each, abundant water resources, and significant conventional and non-conventional energy reserves. Peru also holds importance because it borders four countries and has substantial hydro potential yet to be developed.</p>	<p>(1) There is difficulty in accessing certain data, particularly for Venezuela.</p> <p>(2) The advance of liquid natural gas (LNG) and smart grids were not included in the analysis.</p> <p>(3) Assumptions about the continuity of current integration projects introduce uncertainties in the modelling.</p>	[37]

Developing a community of practice around an open source energy modelling tool	Not applicable	Modelling	This paper details the code management structure and code updates for OSeMOSYS. It also discusses the community forum and the outreach activities that have successfully fostered a vibrant community of practice around OSeMOSYS.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	[44]
Influence of Electrification Pathways in the Electricity Sector of Ethiopia-Policy Implications Linking Spatial Electrification Analysis and Medium to Long-Term Energy Planning	Ethiopia	Case study – Methodology	This work addresses two key questions for Ethiopia's energy planning. First, it explores how Ethiopia can identify internally consistent, least-cost energy pathways that consider the country's financial capacity, technological maturity, environmental constraints, demand growth in different sectors, and medium- to long-term policy goals. Second, it examines how geospatial analyses can enhance energy system modelling by accounting for geospatial drivers in electrification technology choices and improving results with this extension. The study employs a soft-link between the Open-Source energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) for whole-system cost-optimization of Ethiopia's electricity system and the Open-Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET) for geospatial electrification modelling.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 8 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2065	1 region	(1) Although hydropower is being fully exploited across all scenarios, if investments are allowed, the country still diversifies its power generation mix in the future with the integration of renewable energy technologies (RETs) such as solar PV, CSP, wind, geothermal, and biomass. However, if future investments in hydropower and other renewable technologies are constrained by financial limitations, there will likely be a higher reliance on fossil fuel technologies. (2) Improvements in transmission and distribution networks are emphasized across all scenarios and are deemed essential for future development. (4) Domestic constraints on both financial availability and the capacity growth of the power system will impact Ethiopia's ability to fulfill its regional export ambitions. (5) Depending on the scenario, different combinations of grid connections, mini-grids, and standalone solutions will be advisable to achieve comprehensive residential electrification.	(1) Evaluating the Role of Decentralized Technologies (2) Investigating the environmental and socioeconomic impacts of power system investments, with a focus on large hydropower projects in the context of climate variability, future droughts, and their competition with other water uses. (3) Modelling energy storage to understand the evolution of energy markets. (4) Conducting sensitivity analysis to quantify the impact of projected future electricity demand, fuel prices, and technology costs on the electricity supply system. (5) Updating input data in the future using a unified database, which is currently lacking, to enhance the accuracy of modelling results.	[127]

<p>Enhancing energy models with geo-spatial data for the analysis of future electrification pathways: The case of Tanzania</p>	<p>Tanzania</p>	<p>Case study – Methodology</p>	<p>This research explores alternative development pathways for the Tanzanian electricity sector, aiming to deliver reliable and replicable results that can support policy decisions. Additionally, the study introduces an innovative, agile approach that uses geospatial data of the national territory to characterize electricity demand. This geospatial data is also crucial for detailed modelling of various technological solutions, both on-grid and off-grid, to meet demand and expand access at minimal cost using OSeMOSYS.</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>Available as supplementary material at [link]</p>	<p>Intrayear resolution: Unknown Modelling horizon: 2015-2040</p>	<p>1 region</p>	<p>(1) While reducing carbon intensity is more effectively achieved through environmental policies rather than the recently drafted technology policy by the national government, investment requirements are largely dependent on the projected levels of electricity demand. (2) Moving away from a business-as-usual (BAU) scenario, which heavily relies on fossil fuels, is advisable not only for environmental benefits but also to lower electricity costs for end-users and to enhance the diversification of the power system. Additionally, this shift would reduce the national power system's vulnerability to uncertainties associated with the future evolution of both domestic and imported fossil fuels, particularly natural gas prices. (3) Achieving universal access by 2030 is technically feasible, as shown in this study, but presents challenges in reducing carbon intensity or the cost of electricity provision. (4) While on-grid developments are crucial, off-grid renewable solutions should also receive adequate attention to ensure electricity access at the lowest cost, especially in rural areas. Up-to-date, country-specific cost estimates of alternative technologies should guide any planning decisions in this regard.</p>	<p>(1) Enhance the integration between GIS data and the optimization model by increasing flexibility in the potential transition from off-grid to on-grid connections, varying the set of available technologies based on the status of spatial areas, and balancing supply and demand. (2) Increase the number of status categories and improve spatial resolution. (3) Update and refine projections for population development. (4) Incorporate modelling of storage technologies. (5) Evaluate the implications of alternative development pathways for the power sector in terms of potential economic growth and environmental sustainability.</p>	<p>[22]</p>
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<p>Implications to the electricity system of Paraguay of different demand scenarios and export prices to Brazil</p>	<p>Paraguay</p>	<p>Case study - Methodology</p>	<p>This paper examines long-term energy planning for Paraguay using a cost-optimization modelling framework (OSeMOSYS), considering various electricity demand projections linked to electricity export prices to Brazil. Additionally, the modelling outputs, particularly the electricity exports from Itaipu to Brazil, were soft-linked with an input-output project finance model to determine the annual revenues from electricity exports for each scenario.</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>Not available</p>	<p>Intrayear resolution: 9 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2018-2040</p>	<p>1 region</p>	<p>(1) Higher electricity export prices to Brazil from Itaipu could increase government revenues and improve national power infrastructure. If prices remain low, reducing exports to Brazil and using Itaipu's generation domestically while increasing exports to Argentina would be more profitable. (2) As electricity demand grows, further development of the Yacyretá dam by 2026 is essential. (3) Maintaining 2018-level export prices after 2023 could fund investments in economic growth, industrial development, transport infrastructure, electric stoves, and biofuel production, enhancing energy security and boosting the economy.</p>	<p>(1) The scope of this analysis could be expanded to include not only the country's electricity supply system but also other sectors such as transportation and residential areas. Additionally, trade connections with neighbouring countries (Bolivia, Chile, Uruguay), demand-side management, energy efficiency measures, and consumer behaviour should be considered. (2) Modelling the storage capabilities of hydro power plants could enhance the operational flexibility and optimize the utilization of hydro power. (3) Analyzing demand drivers under various scenarios could help capture potential future changes in socio-economic factors (e.g., population, GDP). (4) Updating some of the techno-economic parameters derived from international sources related to future power generation technologies with data from local sources. (5) Investigating the macro-economic impacts (e.g., exports, revenues, employment, GDP) associated with the energy sector's development using a top-down modelling approach. An electricity model for Paraguay that employs both modelling approaches could provide comprehensive policy insights into the interplay between the economy and the energy sector. (6) Given the significant influence of water availability in the Paraná</p>	<p>[26]</p>
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										River on the country's power generation mix, examining a climate change scenario would be essential.	
Comparative effectiveness of environmental regulation instruments: Case of the Moroccan electricity mix	Morocco	Case study	This paper aims to assess the impact of a carbon tax and an emission standard on the integration of renewable energy technologies (RET) into the Moroccan electricity mix using a bottom-up modelling framework for optimization. Through an economic analysis of the results, authors demonstrate that a carbon tax offers a stronger incentive for investment in renewable energy compared to an emission standard.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: Unknown Modelling horizon: 2015-2040	1 region	(1) An adaptation of the emission target scenario, which is one of the most cost-effective options in terms of the average cost of electricity generation compared to the carbon tax scenario, will result in cumulative benefits in terms of incremental savings over the baseline scenario due to reduced fuel costs and conventional energy technology operation and maintenance (O&M) costs over the studied period. (2) The carbon tax directly incentivizes the deployment of renewable energy technologies (RET) in the generation system, unlike emission standards. However, its feasibility requires a fully liberalized electricity market, which is not yet established in Morocco. (3) The transition from a conventional energy-based system to one reliant on renewable energy in Morocco faces two major challenges: the lack of market incentive mechanisms for the development of these new technologies and the absence of a well-defined local industrial policy for manufacturing the necessary capital equipment, which would help reduce the high cost of RET.	(1) Evaluation of the short-term impacts of carbon tax and emission targets on the optimal Moroccan electricity system. (2) Application of the stochastic OSeMOSYS approach to explore the impact of a carbon tax and an emission standard on the electricity mix in a non-perfect market situation.	[159]
Decarbonising the transport and energy sectors: Technical feasibility and	Costa Rica	Case study - Methodology	This paper outlines an innovative approach that integrates qualitative and quantitative methods to develop a decarbonization	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 2 timeslices	1 region	(1) Emissions reduction is achieved through the intensive electrification of the transport sector, encompassing private,	(1) Investigate how demand-side management could benefit the decarbonization process.	[28]

socioeconomic impacts in Costa Rica			<p>pathway for the transport and energy sectors included in Costa Rica's National Development Plan (NDP). We present a detailed narrative co-created through a stakeholder-driven back-casting participatory process, which led to a deep-decarbonization scenario compatible with achieving net-zero emissions by 2050. Additionally, we discuss the collaboration and co-creation process between academia and stakeholders that produced the modeling tool currently used in long-term energy policy dialogues in the country. Furthermore, we describe how these narratives were modeled using the OSeMOSYS-CR tool and present the resulting key technical and socioeconomic outcomes.</p>				Modelling horizon: 2020-2050		<p>public, and freight fleets. (2) Energy efficiency, a modal shift towards public transport and active mobility, as well as reduced demand due to digitalization and teleworking, are also identified as key drivers towards deep decarbonization. (3) The National Decarbonization Plan, which is compatible with achieving net-zero emissions by mid-century, brings benefits in terms of health, productivity (due to reduced congestion), and fewer accidents, thereby demonstrating its feasibility and socioeconomic advantages.</p>	<p>(2) Examine inherent uncertainties related to technological costs, demands, efficiencies, and technology availability to assess their effects on technical viability and socioeconomic impacts. (3) Explore fiscal options to offset the potential fiscal impact resulting from the decarbonization of the transport sector. (4) Study decarbonization pathways for the agriculture, water, and land use sectors.</p>	
Climate Change Mitigation Policies in the Transportation Sector in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	Brazil	Case study	<p>This study examines climate change mitigation policies targeting light-duty electric vehicles (LDEVs) in the transportation sector of Rio de Janeiro state, Brazil, over the period 2016–2050. Using the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS), we analyse scenarios involving increased adoption of LDEVs over various time frames, the implementation of a CO2 emission restriction policy, the exclusion of fossil fuels from the power mix, and a combination of these policies.</p>	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	<p>Intrayear resolution: 6 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2016-2050</p>	1 region	<p>(1) Carbon pricing is the most effective way to reduce CO2 emissions in an energy system with significant limitations in renewable energy generation. Conversely, setting targets for clean transportation adoption sends market signals to manufacturers and consumers, allowing them to adjust their behaviour optimally. A policy that combines both approaches may be the best option for decarbonizing transportation. (2) While implementing a carbon tax can enhance the decarbonization of transportation more effectively than merely adopting electric vehicles (EVs), its impact may not</p>	<p>An analysis that encompasses all road passenger transportation technologies and services, considering the substitution and complementarity effects among them in the presence of emission reduction policies (such as carbon taxes and others), as well as the economic impacts of these policies on society.</p>	[19]

									be immediately apparent in the transportation sector due to technological lock-in and a high dependency on liquid fuels.		
The Effect of Electric Vehicle Deployment on Renewable Electricity Generation in an Isolated Grid System: The Case Study of Cyprus	Cyprus	Case study	This paper focuses on the partial electrification of the transport sector as a cost-effective measure to reduce carbon dioxide emissions in the isolated grid system of Cyprus. The study evaluates the impact of electric vehicle deployment on the share of renewable electricity generation, electricity costs, and carbon dioxide emissions.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 63 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2020-2035	1 region	(1) Electrification of the transport sector can facilitate the integration of a higher share of renewable energy technologies into Cyprus's electricity supply, leading to reduced carbon dioxide emissions without increasing electricity prices. (2) A significant increase in the number of charging points is necessary to support the envisioned electric vehicle deployment. Additionally, the development of a broader smart grid is required to implement smart charging. (3) Institutional infrastructure must also be established to enable consumer participation in the future electricity market. The adoption of time-of-use electricity tariffs will promote vehicle charging during periods of low electricity demand or peak renewable energy generation.	(1) Assessing the impact of different electric vehicle charging profiles on the power generation mix. (2) Developing a scenario that assumes the operation of a vehicle-to-grid system to evaluate its impact on renewable energy integration, electric vehicle deployment, and the outlook for electric storage investments. (3) Adoption of demand profiles based on local data can be facilitated as such data becomes available over time.	[52]
Decarbonization of Australia's Energy System: Integrated Modelling of the Transformation of Electricity, Transportation, and Industrial Sectors	Australia	Modelling	This paper examines several potential decarbonization strategies for Australia's energy system through a multi-sector, multi-regional framework. It offers cost-effective technology mix solutions for Australia, detailed at the state level, and includes a comprehensive depiction of various flexibility options such as regional	Based on GENESYS-MOD framework. New parameters, variables, and equations for: 1) Representation of inter-regional power transmission 2) Limits of the ramp-up and ramp-down of generation from	Mathematical modelling is available at the article in the Appendix Code implementation is not available Code version: Math Prog	Most of data is available in the Appendix [link]	Intrayear resolution: 8 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2050 with annual time steps until 2025 followed by 5-year time steps through 2050	7 regions	(1) Significant investments in wind and solar PV are crucial for decarbonizing Australia's energy system, driven by the increasing electricity demand due to the strong electrification of connected energy sectors. (2) A diverse renewable energy supply, achieved through an optimal mix of solar PV and wind, along	(1) Conduct further policy-oriented research to identify major implementation barriers and develop effective sectoral policy frameworks, proposing new market designs to facilitate Australia's energy system transition. (2) Undertake follow-up research to include additional energy sectors in the analysis, moving	[55]

			interconnection and sector coupling across cement, steel, electricity, and transport.	different power plant technologies 3) Limit of the growth of electric cars					with the spatial smoothing effects of a robust transmission grid, results in a lower need for storage compared to a solar-dominated supply with limited inter-regional connectivity. (3) Shifts in transportation modes and an overall reduction in energy-intensive transport activities help decrease final (fossil) energy consumption in the transport sector during the transition period until the electrification of transport achieves a breakthrough. (4) Accelerating Australia's low-carbon energy transition involves several measures: enhancing state-level renewable energy targets and incentives for their deployment and expansion, internalizing external costs through carbon pricing, setting a binding national target for 100% renewable energy with phase-out dates for fossil fuel generation, particularly coal power plants, swiftly replacing inefficient technologies across all energy sectors, providing direct subsidies or tax incentives for electric vehicles to expedite fleet electrification, and promoting efficient and cost-effective public transport systems, car-sharing concepts, and safe infrastructure for bicycles and e-bikes.	towards a fully integrated energy system that also considers the agriculture and land-use sector and non-CO2 greenhouse gases (e.g., methane, N2O, and fluorinated gases). (3) Perform additional studies detailing various mitigation pathways for the steel and cement industries, considering techno-economic uncertainties, and include other emission-intensive industry sectors. (4) Investigate the implications of inter-regional hydrogen transport and the role of long-term hydrogen/gas storage in balancing the variability of intermittent renewables, and explore the potential for exporting renewable hydrogen from Western Australia to Southeast Asia within deep-decarbonization scenarios. (5) Enhance the applied methodology by increasing regional resolution to address sub-regional discrepancies in energy demand and renewable supply, and conduct detailed simulations of intra-regional power transmission grids. (6) Analyze the impact of different storage technologies on providing the necessary balancing for large-scale integration of variable renewable energy sources (VRES), incorporating higher time-resolution in the model or coupling with a dispatch model.	
Electrification pathways for Tanzania: Implications for the	Tanzania	Case study - Methodology	This study presents a methodology for modelling alternative electrification scenarios for Tanzania and estimating their potential	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available with subscription to Elsevier [link]	Intrayear resolution: Unknown	1 region	(1) Although all electrification pathways lead to significant economic growth over the observed period, the	(1) Enhance the characterization of household consumption in the macroeconomic model by distinguishing between	[124]

economy and the environment			economic and environmental impacts. The analysis employs both the OSeMOSYS open-source power system optimization model and the Leontief Input-Output model, which is based on the Tanzanian Social Accounting Matrix.				Modelling horizon: 2015-2030		environmental impacts of expanding the electricity sector are equally notable. Policies aimed at decarbonizing electricity generation are effective in reducing the country's carbon intensity. However, to limit the rise in emissions as the economy grows, it is crucial to implement energy efficiency and/or decarbonization policies in other sectors, particularly the industrial sector, which is currently the largest contributor to carbon emissions. (2) Changes in household consumption habits may significantly affect the country's carbon emissions, as higher average incomes lead to increased consumption of carbon-intensive goods and services. This suggests that when designing policies and interventions to achieve sustainable development goals, the Government of Tanzania should also focus on reducing the carbon intensity of the service sector.	urban and rural consumers, as well as considering new access to electricity and improvements in capacity or reliability. Additionally, address issues related to poverty and income inequality. (2) Examine the impact of alternative policies on other sectors of the economy, such as energy efficiency measures and instruments designed to reduce carbon emissions.	
Development of functionalities for improved storage modelling in OSeMOSYS	Not applicable	Modelling	This study proposes an enhanced formulation of the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) to better represent energy and resource storage processes. Specifically, it focuses on incorporating storage losses for both hydropower generation dams and electricity storage batteries.	New parameters, variables, and equations for: 1) Accounting of calendar life losses for battery technologies. 2) Accounting of dam evapotranspiration losses.	Mathematical modelling is not available Code implementation is not available Code version: Math Prog	Not available	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	(1) Apply the enhanced modelling framework to a real-world case study. (2) Investigate the linearization of cycle life losses for batteries	[141]
Storage end effects: An evaluation of common storage modelling assumptions	Not applicable	Modelling	This paper evaluates various methods for addressing end effects of storage in energy system models. We aim to	Three alternative storage modelling formulations are described:	Not available Code version: MathProg	Not available	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	(1) Investigate the impact of different variable renewable energy (VRE) profiles on the value of storage.	[142]

			compare these different model structures and demonstrate how the chosen structure affects storage operation. Specifically, we compare the storage operation across three modelling strategies: requiring refilling of the storage at the end of the model period, using a look-ahead window for storage, and valuing storage at the end of the model period.	1) Look ahead structure 2) Valuing storage structure 3) Storage utilization measurement						(2) Conduct further research into the assumptions and implications of storage modelling to ensure that energy system models accurately approximate the optimal operation of storage within the system.	
Flexibility requirements and electricity system planning: Assessing inter-regional coordination with large penetrations of variable renewable supplies	Canada	Modelling	The paper explores the impact of flexibility requirements on interregional transmission and generation fleets within a two-region electricity system featuring high levels of variable renewable (VR) generation. Using a long-term hybrid expansion and dispatch model, the regions are jointly optimized. This study adds to the literature by integrating constraints from short-term phenomena, specifically VR energy output, into a long-term capacity expansion model, considering potential offsetting resources such as hydroelectric generation and interregional transmission.	New parameters, variables, and equations for: 1) Explicit modelling of cascaded hydroelectric systems. 2) Capture of short-term constraints on the electrical system such as minimum generation level, maximum output changes between time steps (ramping), and capacity allocated to regulation. 3) Requirement of additional flexibility to support VR generation.	Mathematical modelling is available at the article (it requires Elsevier subscription) Code implementation is not available Code version: Math Prog	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 32 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2060	2 regions	(1) Transmission between British Columbia and Alberta has the potential to support high levels of wind generation under current carbon policies. (2) In the long term, the need for flexibility leads to the replacement of more efficient but less flexible generators with those that are less efficient but more flexible. (3) Although hydroelectricity offers some flexibility, its capacity is insufficient for the demands of a high-VR system. Existing hydroelectric generators are supplemented by a combination of simple cycle gas turbines (SCGTs) and combined cycle gas turbines (CCGTs) for peaking, ramping, and regulation services. To fully decarbonize the electricity sector, it is essential to develop technologies that provide flexibility services and establish the policy and market environment to support these technologies. (4) Two key value components—flexibility and resource	(1) Identifying optimal locations for future wind farms through geospatial analysis. (2) Evaluating alternative forecasts for fuel prices and technology costs over the modelling period. (3) Enhancing models to better simulate curtailment behaviour. (4) Determining the optimal system structure for incorporating specific resource additions to ensure system reliability.	[143]

									complementarity— indicate that interregional transmission can, in some cases, deliver more services at lower costs than local solutions like fast-ramping generators and resource diversification.		
Electrification of road transportation with utility controlled charging: A case study for British Columbia with a 93% renewable electricity target	Canada	Case study	We examine the impact of electrifying the entire road vehicle fleet on the electricity system, covering passenger vehicles as well as light, medium, and heavy-duty freight and transit vehicles. A bottom-up linear programming model is utilized to determine the optimal generation capacity and dispatch needed to meet an exogenous demand. British Columbia (B.C.) serves as the case study due to its high proportion of freight vehicles compared to passenger vehicles, ambitious transportation electrification targets, and existing low-carbon generation mix. The scenarios explore different levels of utility-controlled charging (UCC) adoption and the effects of implementing a renewable portfolio standard aimed at achieving 93% renewable energy penetration. Additionally, the value of UCC per vehicle-year is quantified.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available with subscription to Elsevier [link]	Intrayear resolution: 80 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2055	1 region	(1) Eliminating the renewable portfolio standard (RPS) of a minimum 93% share of electricity from renewable sources would reduce the carbon reduction impact of transportation electrification, resulting in higher carbon abatement costs. To achieve deep decarbonization targets, combined measures in both the electricity and transportation sectors are necessary. (2) The use of renewable generators can facilitate the expansion of the electricity system to meet the demand from electric vehicles while keeping emissions low and maintaining minimal increases in electricity prices compared to a reference scenario without electrification. (3) Electrifying the transport system can be accomplished with minimal additional costs to the electricity system. The total system capacity expansion requirements may not be proportionally representative of system cost increases due to the decreasing costs of wind and solar PV generators. (4) Utility-controlled charging (UCC) provides system benefits by reducing peak demand and shifting it to low-demand hours. The study	(1) Investigate the ancillary service requirements for electrifying the transport sector, including using a unit commitment model. (2) Incorporate ramping constraints into the analysis. (3) Evaluate the broader system costs of electrifying the road transportation sector, taking into account the necessary infrastructure changes.	[53]

									<p>suggests that UCC can displace demand from early evening peaks to midday when solar PV generation is abundant, thereby lowering system costs.</p> <p>(5) UCC reduces excess energy generation and the required generation capacity, but the marginal impact diminishes with the number of participating vehicles. This relatively low economic benefit of UCC may attract a limited number of participants, highlighting its limited capability as a demand-side management application.</p>		
Impacts of energy efficiency policies on the integration of renewable energy	Tunisia	Modelling	<p>This paper demonstrates how a planned decrease in power system reliability, without affecting energy access, could enhance the integration of renewable energies. We have linked an energy efficiency measure, specifically peak clipping through scheduled outages, to the power system reliability factor. This factor has been incorporated into the energy planning model, Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS), to evaluate two scenarios for Tunisia with varying renewable energy source (RES) penetration targets.</p>	<p>Introduction of the concept of Loss-of-Load probability (LOLP) to determine the power system reliability as a parameter.</p> <p>Modification of the energy balance equation to account for system reliability.</p>	<p>Mathematical modelling is briefly described in the article (it requires Elsevier subscription)</p> <p>Code implementation is not available</p> <p>Code version: Math Prog</p>	Not available	<p>Intrayear resolution: 16 timeslices</p> <p>Modelling horizon: 2010-2030</p>	1 region	<p>(1) Variations in system reliability significantly impact generating capacities, particularly where investments in conventional technologies dominate.</p> <p>(2) A peak clipping initiative could be implemented alongside high renewable energy penetration to minimize costs and make investments in renewable technologies more profitable.</p> <p>(3) Load shedding could be better utilized by promoting scheduled load shedding methods for high energy consumers, coupled with outage tariffs.</p>	<p>Modelling load shifting to provide insights into renewable energy capacity investments and identify which energy efficiency actions are most suitable for integrating renewable energy into the power system.</p>	[81]
Cost minimization for fully renewable electricity systems: A Mauritius case study	Mauritius	Case study	<p>This paper employs a cost-effectiveness approach to identify the least expensive pathways for obtaining electricity from renewable sources with minimal or no reliance on fossil fuels. Mauritius serves as a useful case study to demonstrate cost minimization for</p>	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	<p>Intrayear resolution: 732 timeslices</p> <p>Modelling horizon: 2040</p>	1 region	<p>(1) Strong policy measures, such as limits on fossil fuel use and subsidies for renewable fuels, would be necessary to achieve 100% renewable electricity.</p> <p>(2) Sugarcane could form the basis of a new bagasse-bioethanol-</p>	<p>(1) Evaluate the availability and cost of land needed to develop the required installed capacities for solar PV and wind energy.</p> <p>(2) Assess the comprehensive impacts of large-scale pumped-hydro storage by studying the interrelationships among</p>	[107]

			renewable electricity and exemplifies the type of electricity transition that will eventually be required in more complex electric grids worldwide.						<p>solar-wind renewable energy industry. This study shows that such a system can reliably provide sufficient electricity to meet demand day and night throughout the year at a cost comparable to current electricity generation.</p> <p>(3) Demand-side management with smart energy systems could engage domestic, industrial, and service-sector stakeholders, potentially reducing both total costs and land requirements.</p> <p>(4) Constructing a network of lower reservoirs for pumped-hydro storage could address two needs: allowing grid managers to dispatch electricity during peak demand and capturing water flows in lower reservoirs before they are lost to the sea. Additionally, these new reservoirs would increase total water storage on the island, which could be valuable during water shortages.</p>	climate, land use, energy, and water systems (CLEWS) in Mauritius.	
Analyzing Scenarios for the Integration of Renewable Energy Sources in the Mexican Energy System-An Application of the Global Energy System Model (GENeSYS-MOD)	Mexico	Case study	This paper uses numerical techno-economic modelling to examine the impact of current national renewable targets and climate goals on the cost and structural composition of Mexico's energy system. Additionally, an iterative routine is employed to estimate the cost-optimal share of renewable technologies in the energy sector and to analyze the effects of deviating from this share on total discounted system costs,	Not applicable	Not applicable	Some data is available in the Appendix [link]	Intrayear resolution: 16 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2050 computed in 5-year steps	9 regions	<p>(1) Natural gas and photovoltaics dominate the future of the Mexican energy system across all regions, except for the wind-rich East region, which relies heavily on onshore wind turbines for electricity generation. However, an ongoing dependence on natural gas is observed across all scenarios in the intermediate term.</p> <p>(2) Public policies for introducing renewables in the power sector need revision. Current policies</p>	<p>(1) Enhance the time resolution of the model.</p> <p>(2) Connect the broader energy system development discussed in this work with more detailed electricity sector models.</p> <p>(3) Evaluate the cost-optimal transition at a smaller regional level, such as municipalities.</p>	[87]

			emissions, and the energy mix structure.						resemble a scenario without climate policies, are disconnected from the country's climate goals, and fall significantly short of the estimated cost-optimal share of renewables in the power sector. (3) A higher share of renewables in the power sector leads to a greater adoption of electric vehicles in the transportation sector. The heating sector is the last to decarbonize due to substantial cost differences between conventional and renewable heating options. (4) Pursuing more stringent renewable shares in the power sector or stricter climate goals for greenhouse gas mitigation only marginally increases the total cost of the energy and power systems.		
Contributions of shared autonomous vehicles to climate change mitigation	Austin, Texas, USA	Modelling	The paper presents an energy system optimization model that integrates the electricity and transport sectors, calculates endogenous technology adoption, and differentiates between Shared Autonomous Vehicles (SAVs) and privately owned vehicles (POVs) to investigate the contributions of SAVs to climate change mitigation.	1) Constraints to ensure that privately owned vehicles (POVs) are non-dispatchable, meaning the proportion of vehicle types operating in each time slice matches their capacity share within the POV fleet. 2) A sophisticated formulation of electric vehicle (EV) charging and vehicle-to-grid (V2G) capabilities to guarantee that charging, discharging (V2G), driving, and being	Not available Code version: GAMS	Data will be made available on request	Intrayear resolution: Unknown Modelling horizon: 2020-2050	1 region	(1) The SAV fleet is an advantageous market segment for HEVs, PHEVs, and BEVs due to high utilization rates that make vehicles with higher capital costs but lower variable costs more appealing. Even without carbon policy, SAV fleets in our scenarios electrify rapidly and extensively. (2) Transitioning to SAVs results in significant cost savings by meeting vehicle travel demand with a smaller number of vehicles, thereby reducing capital investment needs. (3) The ability to optimally schedule eSAV charging is a more critical factor for achieving positive	(1) Include the costs of charging and refuelling infrastructures, which vary by vehicle technology and differ between POV and SAV variants. (2) Optimize ePOV charging. (3) Model automation and ridesharing as separate entities. (4) Combine private and shared Vehicle Miles Travelled (VMT) demands to enable competition between these two modes for market share. Implement this approach using a discrete choice model, such as a logit model, for mode shares and technology adoption.	[54]

				<p>idle are mutually exclusive activities at both the vehicle and time slice levels.</p> <p>3) Constraints on annual capacity growth rates by technology to prevent unreasonably rapid expansion. These constraints are endogenous, with the allowable new capacity in one model period dependent on the total capacity from the previous period.</p>					<p>environmental and economic outcomes than the travel demand effect of SAV adoption. Optimized charging schedules ensure that eSAVs are charged with low-cost, carbon-free power, helping the system avoid additional investments in generation capacity or battery storage.</p> <p>(4) SAVs can significantly contribute to climate change mitigation under various parameter settings. Policymakers should implement necessary regulations and infrastructure to support their expansion, such as special electricity rate structures or subsidies/tax credits for SAV fleet operators.</p>		
<p>Representation of Balancing Options for Variable Renewables in Long-Term Energy System Models: An Application to OSeMOSYS</p>	Not applicable	Modelling	<p>This paper presents and integrates stand-alone, independent modules to calculate the costs and benefits of flexible generation options within the open-source energy investment modelling framework, OSeMOSYS. These added modules enhance the modelling capacity by incorporating (a) ramping costs, (b) non-linear efficiency decreases at partial load operation, and (c) refurbishment of existing units into the cost minimization objective function of OSeMOSYS.</p>	<p>New parameters, variables, equations, and modifications are focused on:</p> <p>1) Introducing costs for flexible operation based on exogenously defined reserve capacity requirements.</p> <p>2) Including two efficiency values for each technology—one at full load and one at partial load.</p> <p>3) Allowing a refurbishment configuration for specific technologies, chosen by the user through a "tag." This involves enabling two configurations or versions of a</p>	<p>Mathematical modelling is available at the article in the supplementary material</p> <p>Code implementation is available at the article in the supplementary material</p> <p>Code version: MathProg</p>	<p>Available at [link]</p>	<p>Intrayear resolution: 16 timeslices</p> <p>Modelling horizon: 2014-2040</p>	1 region	<p>The enhanced modelling framework is valuable for studying long-term investment options in scenarios with high renewable penetration. Its application to a test case study provides two main insights: first, ramping costs and decreased partial load efficiency can affect the competitiveness of generation technologies in providing reserve capacity; second, refurbishing existing power generation units may offer attractive options for providing the flexibility needed to support variable renewables. Both effects are observed in the long term and can influence infrastructure investment decisions to achieve decarbonization targets.</p>	<p>1) Introduce additional functionalities to calculate reserve capacity demand based on the penetration and variability of intermittent renewables.</p> <p>2) Apply the enhanced framework to real case studies with more complex energy mixes and actual cost trends to derive policy insights.</p>	[144]

				technology: the old version represents the original power plant, and the new version represents the refurbished one.							
Impact of land requirements on electricity system decarbonisation pathways	Alberta, Canada	Modelling	This study explores emission reduction pathways for the electricity supply system while considering land area as a limiting resource. It introduces and defines the Land Area Impact (LAI) as the physical footprint of infrastructure (e.g., buildings, flooded areas of hydropower reservoirs), the space between structures (e.g., areas between wind turbines in a wind farm and spacing between solar arrays), and the land area affected by fuel resource extraction (e.g., open-pit coal mines, natural gas well pads), but excludes the area used for electricity transmission.	The code is expanded by adding land area impact factors and optional land area constraints to: 1) Quantify the land area impacts associated with electricity production. 2) Investigate alternative technology mixes and the cost trade-offs in land-constrained scenarios.	Not available Code version: MathProg	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 48 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2060	1 region	1) Transitioning from a fossil fuel-based power system to one based on wind and solar energy can result in a tenfold increase in the land area affected by electricity generation within the next 45 years. This is a conservative estimate since dispersed wind and solar farms will need more transmission infrastructure than centralized thermal generators, and this study excludes transmission-related land area impacts. 2) A decarbonized electricity supply system still requires significant dispatchable capacity if grid-scale storage is unavailable, such as from fossil fuel generators with CCS or dispatchable renewable sources. 3) It is possible to create an alternative electricity supply system that achieves similar carbon emission reductions while impacting a smaller land area, but this comes at higher costs. This system would utilize low-carbon technologies (like CCS), rooftop solar, geothermal energy, and biomass.	Modelling grid-scale storage technologies	[59]
OSeMOSYS-PuLP: A Stochastic Modeling Framework for Long-Term Energy Systems Modeling	Not applicable	Modelling	This paper introduces a methodological framework for an empirical deterministic-stochastic modelling approach that leverages large real-world datasets for long-term	OSeMOSYS-PuLP comprises standard Python code and software libraries, including PuLP, Pandas, Numpy, and xlrd.	Code implementation is available at [link] Code version: MathProg	Available in the supplementary material at [link]	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	(1) Develop a data-processing infrastructure to automate data preparation with periodic updates of input datasets for OSeMOSYS-PuLP at all	[115]

			energy systems modelling. A new software system, "OSeMOSYS-PuLP," was developed. This new code implementation of the open-source energy modeling system (OSeMOSYS) significantly extends the framework by incorporating Monte Carlo simulations (MCS).	The new code significantly extends the functionality of the OSeMOSYS modelling framework by incorporating Monte Carlo simulations (MCS). Users can select from predefined or user-defined probability distributions provided through the input data file. It also manages input and output data files in spreadsheet format. Lastly, OSeMOSYS-PuLP is written as a concrete model to make the code more intuitive and easier to understand the logic of the equation system.						stages of the energy system. (2) Develop analysis software to generate directly publishable tables and figures from the OSeMOSYS-PuLP output dataset. (3) Develop a graphical user interface for OSeMOSYS-PuLP to make the software system accessible to all types of users and independent from external spreadsheet software.	
Electricity system and emission impact of direct and indirect electrification of heavy-duty transportation	Alberta, Canada	Case study	This work examines the long-term impacts on the electricity system of converting the heavy-duty (HD) transport sector to battery electric vehicles (BEVs) or fuel cell vehicles (FCVs). A bottom-up linear programming model is used to determine which generators are built to meet both conventional electricity system demand and the load from charging electric vehicles. The study explores the effects of different HD vehicle charging profiles and the implementation of carbon taxes.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 48 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2060	1 region	1) Without carbon taxes, the electrification of heavy-duty (HD) transportation results in only modest emission reductions. This indicates that, even with the electrification of HD vehicles, additional policies are required to lower the carbon intensity of the electricity system and achieve significant emission reductions. 2) Although using batteries to manage variability achieves similar emission reduction outcomes, it is much more costly to store excess energy in batteries compared to hydrogen (H2), leading to higher abatement costs. This	1) Increase the temporal resolution and include ramping constraints for thermal electricity generators. 2) Consider additional battery storage and transport technology options, such as catenary systems, induction charging, or rail.	[85]

									implies that transitioning to hydrogen fuel cell vehicles (FCVs) instead of battery electric vehicles (BEVs) results in lower carbon abatement costs.		
Determinants of energy futures-a scenario discovery method applied to cost and carbon emission futures for South American electricity infrastructure	South America	Case study – Methodology	This paper employs a 'scenario discovery' method, creating a wide array of scenarios based on ranges of selected input parameters, or determinants. These scenarios are evaluated using key metrics, or attributes. Data-mining tools are then used to analyze the relationships between important attributes and their determinants, helping to understand the multidimensional solution space. By focusing on South America, the paper translates a collection of long-term electricity supply scenarios into actionable policy insights.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 48 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2013-2063	1 region	(1) Fossil fuel prices do not significantly impact either the overall system cost or the transition to low-carbon futures in South America. However, the cost of capital is a key determinant, with lower capital costs favoring more capital-intensive, often low-carbon technologies. Financial interventions, such as subsidizing interest rates or offering tax breaks for low-carbon technologies, and political interventions, like removing barriers in the investment environment (e.g., streamlining the construction process), can help mitigate high capital costs due to perceived risk. (2) Demand reduction significantly affects both emissions and scenario costs. If cost-effective, energy efficiency measures can reduce electricity demand without impacting major economic processes or living standards. Additionally, demand-side management (DSM) systems can provide peak shaving, reducing the need for peaking or backup power plants. (3) South America possesses significant natural resources and substantial interconnection and trade capacity. These factors can protect the region from relying on expensive	(1) Analyze the impact of energy efficiency measures and demand-side management (DSM) as strategic levers. (2) Include the 'degree of inter-connectedness' as an additional dimension in the scenario matrix. (3) Conduct an analysis of potential carbon leakage among countries.	[117]

									<p>generation options that are higher up the supply curve.</p> <p>(4) To achieve a zero-emission system, the reserve margin for zero-emission scenarios must be supplied by low-carbon technologies. To avoid extra installed capacity and potential stranded assets, idle fossil capacity can be used to supply the reserve margin while investing in negative emissions options, such as carbon capture and storage (CCS) in the forestry sector. Another approach is to lower capital costs by providing financial incentives for stakeholders to invest in larger renewable capacity today.</p>		
<p>Are emission reduction policies effective under climate change conditions? A backcasting and exploratory scenario approach using the LEAP-OSeMOSYS Model</p>	Australia	Case study	<p>This study leverages the LEAP-OSeMOSYS model to assess the effectiveness of emission reduction policies in an optimized future power system up to 2050. It emphasizes the economic impacts, including social costs, sales revenue, electricity production costs, long-run marginal costs, cost-benefit analysis, and sensitivity analysis. The aim is to explore the changes in investment, fuel, and operational costs for future power generation technologies.</p>	Not applicable	Not applicable	<p>Available with subscription to Elsevier [link]</p>	<p>Intrayear resolution: 9 timeslices</p> <p>Modelling horizon: 2014-2050</p>	7 regions	<p>(1) Higher integration of renewables into the future energy system will significantly enhance energy affordability, reliability, and reduce GHG emissions, even under future climate conditions.</p> <p>(2) The techno-economic and environmental analysis shows that the most effective approach to combating the impact of climate change on the electrical system is to adapt the system to future climate conditions while mitigating GHG emissions. This approach involves transitioning Australia's current stock of fossil fuel plants to renewables and battery storage systems, which may pose a short-term challenge regarding available investment funds.</p>	<p>(1) Analyze the issue of excessive biomass consumption for electricity generation, which can lead to increased emissions and negatively impact biodiversity.</p> <p>(2) Assess the cross-sectoral impacts of emission reduction policies.</p> <p>(3) Vary the price and cost of input parameters to further examine the model's sensitivity.</p> <p>(4) Extend the policy scenario options and explore additional policy pathways.</p> <p>(5) Examine the impact of climate change on available wind and hydropower data to model its effects on the electricity sector in Australia or other countries.</p>	[119]

									(3) A carbon tax proves to be more effective than an emission reduction target. In the context of climate change, generation expansion options based on non-renewable energy pathways seem less optimal.		
Open source-based modeling of power plants retrofit and its application to the Korean electricity sector	Republic of Korea	Modelling	This study introduces an innovative approach to modelling power plant retrofits using the bottom-up formulation of OSeMOSYS, which offers extensive flexibility in energy systems modelling. This approach has been applied to the Korean electricity sector.	New parameters, variables, equations, and code modifications are focused on modelling different features of retrofitting of power plants: (1) Change of plant (or operation) characteristics (2) Lifetime extension (3) Capacity expansion (4) Installation time	Mathematical modelling is available at the article Model code will be made available on request. Code version: MathProg	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 5 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2029	1 region	(1) Retrofitting existing old plants instead of retiring them may slow down the construction of new plants. (2) While the reduction in CO2 emissions may not seem substantial, significant cost savings can be achieved due to the benefits of retrofitting, such as efficiency improvement, capacity expansion, and lifetime extension. (3) Sensitivity analysis shows that even a slight improvement in generation efficiency can result in noticeable cost savings. However, the effects of lifetime extension on cost savings and emissions reduction appear marginal and are limited to the analysis period's duration. (4) The cost-effectiveness of power plant retrofits is evident even when a carbon tax is imposed on emissions. Additionally, retrofitting power plants combined with a carbon tax can lead to further emissions reductions. (5) Retrofitting power plants can be considered a cost-effective mitigation measure in the power generation sector.	(1) Assess the impacts of flexibility on the modelling approach for retrofitting of power plants (2) Include CCS retrofitting as an option	[145]
Soft-linking energy demand and optimisation models for local long-term	Village of Katgaon, India	Case study – Methodology	This study aims to integrate a bottom-up approach for short- and long-term load profile forecasts with an	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available with subscription to Elsevier [link]	Intrayear resolution: 288 timeslices	1 region	(1) Modelling based on socio-economic indicators and integrating short- and long-term	(1) Explore bottom-up simulation models for assessing electricity demand.	[121]

<p>electricity planning: An application to rural India</p>			<p>energy optimization model in a comprehensive rural energy planning procedure. Applied to a small Indian community, the procedure consists of three components: (i) a bottom-up model that projects household electrical appliance usage based on socio-economic indicators for long-term forecasts; (ii) a stochastic load profile generator that uses correlations and user habits to assess coincidence and load factors; (iii) an energy optimization model based on OSeMOSYS to determine the economic optimum.</p>				<p>Modelling horizon: 2014-2034</p>		<p>electricity load dynamics can lead to less arbitrary energy demand scenarios, as it relies on local data on energy habits and projections of household expenditures. (2) Incorrect predictions of long-term electricity demand evolution have direct implications on the costs of energy systems, tariff-setting processes, the profitability of investments promoting off-grid systems in developing contexts, and the local socio-economic sustainability of an energy project.</p>	<p>(2) Implement stochastic modelling frameworks for comprehensive analysis.</p>	
<p>Modelling for power generation sector in Developing Countries: Case of Egypt</p>	<p>Egypt</p>	<p>Case study</p>	<p>This research aims to quantitatively assess future development scenarios for Egypt's power generation sector. The least-cost power generation mix will be identified according to two different electricity demand scenarios and compared with the energy plans announced by the Egyptian government. Additionally, the robustness of the results will be tested through a sensitivity analysis on key exogenous parameters, including costs, efficiency and production targets of energy technologies, capital discount rate, and the availability of water and natural gas resources.</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>Not available</p>	<p>Intrayear resolution: 15 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2008-2040</p>	<p>1 region</p>	<p>(1) The lowest-cost electricity generation mix consistently includes hydropower, natural gas-fired steam cycles, simple and combined cycles, wind power, and PV rooftop technologies. This outcome is primarily due to the low economic cost of these technologies compared to others. Since Egypt's electricity peak load demand occurs at night, investing in large solar power generation utilities is not economically feasible. (2) Based on the sensitivity analysis, the investment costs of renewables, the presence of subsidies on natural gas production, and changes in prospective renewable penetration targets have negligible effects on the future generation mix. In contrast, the results are sensitive to the efficiency of natural gas combined cycle technology, the availability of unrestricted</p>	<p>(1) Enhance the quality and reliability of electricity demand projections. (2) Conduct sensitivity analysis by changing multiple parameters simultaneously to identify potential cross-effects. (3) Apply specific discount rates to different technologies. (4) Broaden the scope of the energy model to include multiple energy carriers (such as heating and cooling) and various national sectors.</p>	<p>[33]</p>

									natural gas supplies, and the values of the capital discount rate.		
Modeling the long-term impact of demand response in energy planning: The Portuguese electric system case study	Portugal	Case study - Methodology	This study integrates long-term planning with the flexibility offered by demand response (DR), examining its impact on avoided installed capacity, investment delays, higher integration of renewables, reduced need for thermal backup capacity, and overall system costs. The authors utilized an extended version of the OSeMOSYS tool by incorporating equations into the optimization model to include DR technology.	Introduction of flexible load modelling proposed by Welsch, 2013.	Not available	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 96 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2050	1 region	(1) The implementation of demand response (DR) consistently reduces both costs and total installed capacity. This reduction is more significant in scenarios with higher renewable capacity and generation, primarily due to avoided investment in installed capacity and increased generation from renewables without any marginal cost. (2) The impact of DR on the overall system generally becomes relevant in terms of capacity expansion and costs after about 15 years of the model period. In scenarios with a higher share of renewables, this impact becomes relevant sooner.	(1) Assess the economic benefits of demand response (DR) in greater detail and evaluate the viability of using DR as a tool to aid in system design and energy dispatch models. (2) Link the capacity expansion model to a dispatch model to compare results across different scenarios and analyze how the geospatial distribution of power plants affects electricity generation and decentralized dispatch. (3) Incorporate geographic information on generation and consumption in Portugal, along with the inclusion of other decentralized technologies such as batteries and electric vehicles, to study their interaction with DR.	[158]
Optimal decarbonization pathways for urban residential building energy services	Austin, Texas, USA	Modelling	This study creates an energy system optimization model to find the least-cost decarbonization pathway for residential building energy services, contributing three novel aspects: (1) It provides a more accurate representation of energy service demand profiles, renewable resource capacity factors, and operational variables by using higher temporal resolution and firmer empirical grounding than previous studies. (2) It employs CitySim software to simulate space heating and cooling demands for four different building efficiency levels. (3) It focuses on the urban scale, unlike the regional, national, or global scopes	It includes modifications to accurately represent residential building services: 1) Requiring that the operational shares of all end-use technologies in a given service demand category match their installed capacity shares. 2) Imposing an upper limit on the new capacity of each technology added in a given year, set as a percentage of the previous year's installed capacity plus a start-up value to allow for	Not available Code version: GAMS	Some data is available in the Appendix of the article with Elsevier subscription [link]	Intrayear resolution: 96 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2050	1 region	(1) The primary strategies for cost-effectively decarbonizing urban residential building energy services are electrifying energy end-uses and decarbonizing electricity generation. (2) As the carbon intensity of the power sector declines, electrification becomes a more effective mitigation tactic, though it reduces the CO2 savings from efficiency improvements. Appliance efficiency has a relatively minor impact, limited to specific services like lighting, space heating, and water heating. (3) The stringency of climate policy significantly influences the optimal decarbonization strategy.	(1) Consider the interactions between the residential buildings sector and other supply and demand components of the energy economy, such as energy commodity markets, industry, commercial buildings, and transportation. 2) Expand the end-use technology options within each service category. (3) Explicitly model the turnover of the residential building stock, including different vintages of homes with specific efficiency parameters. (4) Incorporate endogenous service prices and price-elastic demands.	[122]

			usually found in integrated energy system models.	some initial deployment of new technology options.					For example, upgrading from standard to high-efficiency natural gas furnaces for space heating is optimal under moderate policies but shifts to electrification as carbon constraints become more restrictive. (4) Improving the thermal efficiency of residential buildings results in substantial cost savings and significantly reduces the cost of climate policy. (5) Carbon reduction measures and building energy efficiency standards are complementary regulations that mutually reinforce each other.		
Methodology for energy security assessment considering energy system resilience to disruptions	Lithuania	Methodology	This article introduces a methodology for assessing energy security by evaluating the resilience of energy systems to disruptions. The methodology provides an integrated framework for energy security evaluation, directly focusing on system resilience. The proposed model enhances conventional energy system modelling tools by incorporating the ability to simulate energy systems under stochastic disruptions. Additionally, the methodology offers an energy security metric aimed at quantitatively estimating energy security for future development scenarios or pathways based on system resilience.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: Unknown Modelling horizon: 2015-2030	1 region	The development of renewable energy sources (RES) must be carefully considered and cannot be expedited within a very short time period, as this significantly increases the cost of the energy system and impacts the level of energy security.	(1) Automate the model design to minimize manual interactions. (2) Reduce generation time by reformulating the code and utilizing more powerful solvers. (3) Include additional types of disruptions and parameters. (4) Introduce supplementary energy security metrics. (5) Enhance the calculation of disruption consequences. (6) Apply the methodology to regional case studies.	[114]
Valuing infrastructure investments to reduce curtailment	Alberta, Canada	Modelling	This study incorporates curtailment cost tracking into a medium-term version of the OSeMOSYS linear programming model, demonstrating how accounting for curtailment costs enhances the value	New parameters, variables, equations, and code modifications are introduced to incorporate curtailment costs.	Mathematical modelling is available at the article (with Elsevier subscription)	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 2920 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2030 (single year)	1 region	(1) Investments in storage and dispatchable loads are effective methods to reduce constrained wind energy in the modelled system and enhance the value of infrastructure investments.	(1) Incorporate various levels of curtailment costs by implementing a curtailment cost 'supply stack,' akin to the supply stack used for generation technologies in OSeMOSYS.	[146]

			proposition of infrastructure investments aimed at reducing curtailment. Investments in infrastructure such as storage and dispatchable load technologies are evaluated for a system with high wind penetration.		Model code is not available Code version: MathProg				(2) Higher curtailment costs and increased wind penetration levels result in a larger proportion of the system's overall costs being attributed to curtailment. Including curtailment costs in an energy system model allows for the calculation of the benefits that infrastructure investments might provide in reducing these costs, thus incentivizing the installation of curtailment-reducing technologies. Ignoring these costs can potentially undervalue the benefits of such investments. (3) The value of a dispatchable load remains fairly constant across a wide range of installed capacities, whereas the value of storage infrastructure diminishes as more capacity is installed. For dispatchable loads, it makes no significant difference if competitors also install similar systems, as the investment can still be recouped. In contrast, the value of storage investments is highly dependent on the existing storage capacity in the system, making investment and financing for storage riskier and more challenging.	(2) Model how the infrastructure owner would benefit from the value of infrastructure investments or how the savings would be transferred to the owner. (3) Model the specifics of an actual dispatchable load.	
A Sketch of Bolivia's Potential Low-Carbon Power System Configurations. The Case of Applying Carbon Taxation and Lowering Financing Costs	Bolivia	Case study	This paper explores hypothetical strategies for transforming the Bolivian power generation system to reduce carbon dioxide emissions. It specifically evaluates the impact of the weighted average cost of capital (WACC) on marginal	Not applicable	Not applicable	Supplementary material available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 48 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2013-2040	5 regions	(1) Carbon taxes are a cost-effective policy tool for regulating the diverse range of greenhouse gas emitters. They continuously incentivize the adoption and innovation of carbon-efficient technologies, are	(1) Investigate financial de-risking instruments to assess their potential for lowering the weighted average cost of capital (WACC). (2) Evaluate the cost-effectiveness of strategies	[62]

			abatement cost curves (MACC) when implementing carbon taxation in the power sector. The study employs a bottom-up, least-cost optimization model to illustrate these effects.						straightforward to administer, and do not burden government budgets. (2) High capital costs, reflected by a high weighted average cost of capital (WACC), favor the use of fossil fuels and weaken the impact of carbon pricing. (3) Lowering financing costs for renewable energy technology (RET) investments in developing countries with untapped renewable potential offers policymakers a way to encourage private investment.	aimed at reducing the WACC.	
Coal-to-biomass retrofit in Alberta - value of forest residue bioenergy in the electricity system	Alberta, Canada	Case study	This research calculates the cost of delivering biomass to the plant gate and evaluates the cost and emission benefits of converting coal power units to bioenergy. Utilizing the OSeMOSYS optimization model, the study examines the Alberta electrical system, specifically its planned coal phase-out and renewable energy targets for the mid-term future.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Some data is available in the article with Elsevier subscription [link]	Intrayear resolution: 36 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2010-2060	1 region	(1) While bioenergy has a higher levelized cost of energy (LCOE) compared to wind power, the system benefits from requiring less backup capacity and fewer renewable energy credits (RECs) to meet renewable energy targets when biomass retrofits are permitted. (2) LCOE alone is insufficient for determining the optimal generator mix for cost-effective decarbonization of the electrical system. (3) Scenarios with carbon taxes result in higher overall system costs and abatement costs compared to scenarios utilizing RECs, despite achieving similar decarbonization goals.	(1) Assess the carbon impact of replacing coal with biomass in Alberta and the time required to achieve carbon sequestration parity. (2) Consider the effects of curtailment costs and power purchase agreements (PPA). (3) Include forest carbon stocks and fluxes in the analysis. (4) Evaluate the value of a broader carbon abatement strategy, exploring alternative uses for residual forest biomass (e.g., creating long-life wood products) alongside alternative electricity generation options.	[129]
Combining Behavioral Approaches with Techno-Economic Energy Models: Dealing with the Coupling Non-Linearity Issue	Not applicable	Modelling	This study introduces a novel method to integrate a classical energy model with a share of choice model by externalizing the share of choice. This approach reduces the number of binary variables and maintains linearity, even in complex models. The	New sets, parameters, variables, and constraints are incorporated into the energy model to account for share of choice information. The code adjustment is	Mathematical modelling is available at the article Code implementation is available in the supplementary material at [link]	Available in the supplementary material at [link]	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Develop a model that allows for dynamic variation in government policies, capturing the effects of campaigns as they evolve over time with inertia and erosion factors.	[147]

			method involves three steps: (1) Estimation of Utility Functions: Using standard conjoint analysis techniques, consumers' utility functions are estimated through a survey. (2) Quantification of Consumer Behaviour: A share of choice model translates consumers' behavior into market share data. (3) Integration with Energy Model: The market shares are incorporated into the energy model through specific modelling techniques.	demonstrated through a case study that examines consumer preferences between fluorescent and LED bulbs under two distinct government policies: an information campaign and a subsidy campaign promoting the more efficient LED bulbs.	Code version: MathProg						
From the development of an open-source energy modelling tool to its application and the creation of communities of practice: The example of OSeMOSYS	Not applicable	Modelling	This paper discusses the role of an open-source energy modelling tool in the energy planning process, emphasizing its significance for society. It highlights the relationship between developing an open-source, freely available tool and its application, dissemination, and use for policymaking. Using the Open Source energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) as an example, the paper focuses on the practices established within the community that ensured the framework's development and application were both relevant and scientifically grounded.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	[17]
A Brazilian perspective of power systems integration using OSeMOSYS SAMBA - South America Model Base - and the bargaining power of neighbouring countries: A	South America	Case study – Methodology	This study introduces a methodology aimed at assisting policymakers in international negotiations by using the Shapley value to fairly distribute the benefits of power system integration. It examines three scenarios for expanding the power supply sector in South America,	Not applicable	Not applicable	Some data is available in the article with Elsevier subscription [link]	Intrayear resolution: 48 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2013-2058	14 regions	(1) From a Brazilian perspective, funding strategic hydropower projects abroad would ensure the availability of large amounts of imported electricity, primarily from Peru and Guyana. (2) Although the generation mix will still be	1) Analyze the regulatory aspects of cross-border electricity trade legislation to enhance long-term power sector cooperation across the continent. 2) Investigate the environmental and social sustainability of large hydropower projects,	[135]

cooperative games approach			evaluating the pros and cons of interconnecting power systems between Brazil and its neighbouring countries.						<p>predominantly hydro due to its largely untapped potential, on-shore wind, pulverized coal, and concentrated solar are projected to become significant sources by 2058.</p> <p>(3) Countries with substantial hydro potential but limited financial capacity, such as Bolivia and Guyana, could enhance their power infrastructure through trade agreements with Brazil, boosting their national budgets through electricity trade and reduced fossil fuel expenditures. Additionally, Peru is expected to become a key electricity exporter to Brazil by leveraging its hydro potential in the Peruvian Amazon.</p> <p>(4) Regional integration with neighboring countries could allow Brazil to achieve lower investment and operational costs compared to solely domestic electricity production.</p> <p>(5) Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay, Peru, and Guyana are identified as having the largest bargaining power, either as electricity exporters or importers.</p>	<p>particularly those in the Amazon rainforest.</p> <p>3) Conduct a sensitivity analysis on the contribution of hydropower to reserve margin levels, assessing the impact on hydro reservoirs as cross-border trade increases.</p>	
Fuel-price reform to achieve climate and energy policy goals in Saudi Arabia: A multiple-scenario analysis	Saudi Arabia	Modelling	This study: (i) offers an updated overview of the power market in Saudi Arabia (KSA) using the latest available data; (ii) examines the effects of various price-reform scenarios on the future expansion of the electricity market, focusing on renewable energy integration and CO2	Two model enhancements were added: i) An option to allow the retirement of existing technologies, considering that approximately 50% of today's capacity	Mathematical modelling is not available Code implementation is not available Code version: MathProg	Some data is available in the appendix of the article [link]	Intrayear resolution: Unknown Modelling horizon: 2015-2030	1 region	<p>(1) When emissions are priced, already at 20% of international wholesale fuel prices, a shift from fossil-fuel-based to renewable power generation expansion is projected.</p> <p>(2) The scenarios that do not consider emissions penalties show lower fuel prices result in higher PV</p>	<p>(1) Investigate strategies for implementing phased pricing increases that ensure public acceptance and protect the most vulnerable community members.</p> <p>(2) Assess the potential for demand reduction through stricter energy efficiency standards for buildings and lighting.</p>	[49]

			reduction to meet COP21 (and future COP) commitments; and (iii) enhances the OSeMOSYS model framework by incorporating multiple-scenario analyses and introducing the option for plant retirements, given that more than 40% of the current KSA power plant fleet comprises inefficient gas turbines (GT).	is based on gas turbines. ii) A feature to set a maximum limit for renewable energy penetration, ensuring the results align with the transmission infrastructure's capabilities.					penetration and higher fuel prices result in higher wind penetration (3) Not pricing for emissions requires a fuel price of at least 50% of the international wholesale fuel price to see significant renewable technologies in the final generation mix (4) The overall level of total renewables added is influenced by: a) the renewable policy and strategy of the KSA, including emissions pricing; b) the quality of the grid and limits of the transmission infrastructure; and c) the speed of fuel-price reform and implementation of price caps, as demonstrated in this multiple scenario analysis.	(3) Examine the price and income elasticity of electricity demand and analyze the implications of fuel price changes on overall GDP, covering the utility, industry, and transportation sectors.	
Long-term optimisation model of the Tunisian power system	Tunisia	Modelling	This paper presents a long-term model of Tunisia's electricity system using OSeMOSYS to explore the potential benefits of increasing renewable energy sources (RES) in electricity production. The study begins by examining the unique aspects of Tunisia's electricity system and the necessity of incorporating these features into the model. It then justifies the selection of OSeMOSYS and details the modifications made to include specific system characteristics. Finally, the model is applied to two scenarios: a Business As Usual case and a 30% RES target in electricity production case, spanning the period from 2010 to 2030.	Incorporation of two new elements to the code: 1) limits on the utilization of interconnections 2) Job creation targets	Mathematical modelling is available in the paper Code implementation is not available Code version: MathProg	Some data is available at the article with Elsevier subscription [link]	Intrayear resolution: 16 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2010-2030	1 region	1) Setting job creation targets in the renewable energy (RE) scenario does not significantly change the renewable energy share but does influence technological preferences, favoring decentralized PV despite higher costs. 2) A well-planned long-term energy strategy (2016-2030) with clear objectives can lead to energy independence, diverse resources, social benefits, emission reductions, and competitive electricity costs in the long term. 3) Interconnections may be competitive with other technologies, suggesting that revising the electricity exchange protocol between Tunisia and neighboring countries	(1) Estimate the cost savings from reduced reliance on fossil fuels. (2) Compare the modelled scenarios between OSeMOSYS and electricity network modelling frameworks like WASP to highlight uncertainties in assumptions and identify additional paths influencing output variables. (3) Soft-link with a top-down model that describes demand evolution based on pricing and GDP to find the optimal balance between consumer price pressures and job creation. (4) Introduce constraints to monetize the social benefits of job creation.	[30]

									could uncover new opportunities. 4) Load profile analysis during Ramadan showed the complementarity between wind energy and controllable generation technologies.		
Designing a Model for the Global Energy System GENeSYS-MOD: An Application of the Open-Source Energy Modeling System (OSeMOSYS)	Not applicable	Modelling	This paper outlines a pathway for the global energy system until 2050, introducing a novel application of the open-source energy modeling system, OSeMOSYS, to the community. The model enables detailed energy and emission analyses: GENeSYS-MOD employs a system of linear equations to identify lowest-cost solutions for secure energy supply, while adhering to predefined constraints, particularly focusing on CO2 emissions. The GAMS version of OSeMOSYS has been updated to its latest iteration, with enhancements such as incorporating modal splits for transport, refining the trading system, and augmenting storage capabilities	Different enhancements to the code were included: i) A new 'Transportation' block was added to implement a modal split for distributing passenger or freight kilometres for specific transportation types (e.g., road traffic for passengers). ii) Trade costs, losses, and capacities for fuels between regions were incorporated into the model. iii) The endogenous calculation method for storages was adjusted. iv) The formulation of the renewable energy target was revised.	Mathematical modelling and code implementation are available at [link] Code version: GAMS	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 6 timeslices Maximum modelling horizon: 2020-2050 in 5-year-steps	10 regions	(1) By 2050, the energy mix predominantly comprises wind and solar power, biomass, and hydropower, with lesser contributions from geothermal and tidal sources. Regionally, fossil fuel phase-outs begin as early as 2035, with most fossil fuels replaced by 2045. (2) Strong sector coupling is evident between the power sector, heat sector (utilizing heat pumps and direct electric heating), and transport sector (using battery electric vehicles, electric rails, and hydrogen conversion for mobility where direct electricity use is impractical).	Consider hourly storage and more granular time slices	[154]
South America power integration, Bolivian electricity export potential and bargaining power: An OSeMOSYS SAMBA approach	South America	Case study – Methodology	This study provides a comparative analysis of Bolivia's electricity export potential by examining modelling results from the Bolivian government and OSeMOSYS SAMBA - South America Model Base. Four scenarios, based on different strategic large hydropower combinations, were modelled to highlight the cross-border trade potential between Bolivia and neighbouring countries,	Not applicable	Not applicable	Some data is available in the article with Elsevier subscription [link]	Intrayear resolution: 48 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2013-2058	14 regions	(1) The electricity surplus from strategic large hydro projects in Bolivia presents a significant supply option for Brazil. Thus, the Bolivian government should prioritize bilateral trade agreements with Brazil to position itself as a major electricity exporter on the continent. (2) The theoretical bargaining power of Bolivia in the long-term	(1) Analyze the environmental impacts and social sustainability of large hydropower plants. (2) Assess the cost-competitiveness of Bolivian large hydro projects. (3) Develop an integrated energy resources planning analysis for the entire energy sector.	[136]

			mainly Brazil. Utilizing a Cooperative Games approach, specifically the Shapley value calculation, the bargaining power of Bolivia was identified. This approach offers a clearer understanding of electricity trade opportunities, aiding policymakers in international negotiations and significantly reducing incentives for non-cooperative actions.						cross-border electricity trade is approximately 10%, positioning it as a rival to Peru and Paraguay—both potential major exporters—in meeting Brazil's electricity demand.		
Electrification pathways for Kenya-linking spatial electrification analysis and medium to long term energy planning	Kenya	Case study – Methodology	This paper explores hypothetical scenarios and their implications, investigating possible pathways to achieve the country's electrification targets by 2030. For this study, two modelling tools, OnSSET and OSeMOSYS, were soft-linked to capture both spatial and temporal dynamics. Two electricity demand scenarios were created, representing low and high end-user consumption goals, respectively.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Some data is available at the article [link]	Intrayear resolution: 36 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2012-2040	1 region	(1) Stand-alone technologies like PV can significantly contribute to achieving universal electricity access in Kenya by 2030. (2) The modelled demand levels are crucial in determining the services available to households. Higher demand leads to more grid connections, providing more stable and flexible supply compared to off-grid solutions. (3) Remote areas face higher costs per kWh due to the lack of economies of scale, unlike households in more urban areas.	(1) Conduct multiple iterations between OnSSET and OSeMOSYS for a comprehensive analysis. (2) Evaluate the feasibility of performing multiyear analysis with OnSSET to ensure complete integration with OSeMOSYS. (3) Include feed-in tariffs in the analysis for a more detailed assessment.	[128]
Natural gas in Cyprus: The need for consolidated planning	Cyprus	Case study	This paper evaluates various electricity generation options, including continued reliance on oil products, the use of domestic offshore gas, interim solutions until domestic gas becomes available, LNG imports (both interim and long-term), and accelerated development of renewable generation. The study employs a scenario-based approach to identify least-cost generation strategies while also assessing their flexibility, economic robustness, and impacts on energy security.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Some data is available at the article with Elsevier subscription [link]	Intrayear resolution: 63 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2013-2040	1 region	(1) In a low oil price environment, transitioning from oil to natural gas in the medium term is not essential in terms of fuel costs. (2) A consistent gas demand for electricity generation is unlikely throughout the model period, so additional gas demand should be secured in other sectors, such as through fuel diversification in the transport sector. (3) If natural gas is not available by 2023–2030, investing in renewable energy technologies is	(1) Investigate the potential for abatement technologies through retrofitting existing infrastructure. (2) Examine the deployment of electric vehicles alongside smart grids to create synergies with intermittent generation and facilitate the integration of higher renewable electricity shares. (3) Analyze the potential development and benefits of gas interconnectors with neighboring countries.	[68]

									advisable. However, this would require significant capital investment, as storage and flexible thermal generation options are required to ensure system reliability.		
Hedging the risk of increased emissions in long term energy planning	Alberta, Canada	Modelling	This paper introduces a stochastic risk framework into the OSeMOSYS optimization model to account for uncertainties related to emissions from electricity generation technologies. By defining a risk premium—the extra amount society is willing to pay to mitigate the risk of surpassing the cost-optimal system emissions—the study identifies the generation technology mix that minimizes the likelihood of exceeding this emissions baseline.	New sets, parameters, variables and constraints were added to incorporate risk associated with technology emissions.	Mathematical modelling and code implementation are available at the article with Elsevier subscription [link] Code version: MathProg	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 12 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2010-2060	1 region	(1) While current climate policies eventually encourage the addition of renewables, implementing additional policies for the earlier adoption of solar and wind power could provide a risk hedge against future emissions if nuclear is not an option. (2) Investing in the development of coal with CCS or other unproven low-carbon technologies that can meet baseload demands with lower emissions risk could yield future benefits. (3) If nuclear energy is available, the system predominantly relies on wind and nuclear power, though some flexible generation is necessary for system stability. (4) Nuclear energy is a cost-effective risk hedge against increases in carbon dioxide emissions, even without applying a risk premium.	(1) Differentiate the risks associated with construction emissions from those produced per kWh generated, instead of using levelized emissions. (2) Integrate the risk of carbon leakage in CCS technologies into the model. (3) Develop a framework to incorporate both financial and emissions risks into the model. (4) Extend the study to encompass the entire energy system, not just the electricity system.	[148]
Impact of electrical intertie capacity on carbon policy effectiveness	Alberta and British Columbia, Canada	Case study	This study explores the potential cost and emissions reductions from increased electricity transmission capacity between Alberta and British Columbia, Canada's two westernmost provinces. Alberta relies heavily on fossil fuels, while British Columbia predominantly uses hydroelectric power. A bottom-up model is employed to determine the least-cost electricity generation mix in both	Not applicable	Not applicable	Some data is available at the article with Elsevier subscription [link]	Intrayear resolution: 36 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2010-2060	2 regions	(1) Significant reductions in emissions can be achieved through policy changes alone or in combination with intertie expansion. The emissions changes resulting from intertie expansion are considerably smaller compared to those driven by carbon policy changes. (2) Ensuring consistent carbon policies across interconnected regions is crucial to prevent merely	(1) Enhance the modelling of biomass and natural gas technologies to better reflect their historical performance and behaviour. (2) Investigate the inclusion of price elasticity effects in electricity market models to understand how changes in price affect electricity demand. (3) Study potential future scenarios for Mid-Columbia (Mid-C) power prices and availability to anticipate	[76]

			provinces under various carbon policies.						relocating emissions instead of reducing them. (3) Carbon policies lead to significant emissions reductions by promoting a shift towards low-carbon technologies such as hydro, wind, solar, and fossil fuels with carbon capture and storage (CCS). (4) Achieving a high level of decarbonization is feasible with a relatively modest increase in overall system costs.	market trends and plan accordingly. (4) Improve the timeslice method to better capture short-term variations in electricity demand and generation, allowing for more accurate modelling of fluctuations.	
Proposing an open-source model for unconventional participation to energy planning	Lombardy region, Italy	Modelling	<p>This paper introduces MELiSsa, a localized multi-regional energy system model for the Lombardy region, developed using the open-source OSeMOSYS framework. MELiSsa aims to achieve four primary goals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) Extend the energy planning process to include citizens and experts who are typically not involved, fostering a more inclusive approach. ii) Utilize this expanded participation for crowd-sourced development, leveraging diverse inputs and perspectives. iii) Provide a simple tool for local citizens to understand the technological and behavioural constraints of their energy system, promoting awareness and informed decision-making. iv) Offer a real-case-based platform for interdisciplinary research and academic purposes, with potential applications beyond the Lombardy region. <p>The paper details the structure and input data of MELiSsa and includes a demonstrative analysis to showcase its capabilities.</p>	<p>Some changes and additions were made:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) The CapacityFactor parameter was modified to depend on the mode of operation for certain technologies. (2) Limits were considered on the installed capacity of groups of technologies. (3) The capacities of different technologies were made equal in cases where they represent a single item. (4) An aggregated emission limit was considered for the entire region, including all subregions. 	<p>Mathematical modelling is available in the paper with Elsevier subscription</p> <p>Code implementation is not available</p> <p>Code version: MathProg</p>	<p>Data is available at the article with Elsevier subscription [link]</p>	<p>Intrayear resolution: 8 timeslices</p> <p>Modelling horizon: 2009-2053</p>	11 regions	Not applicable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Create a user-friendly interface to make the model more accessible to users. (2) Analyze methods to simplify the current model and decrease running times. (3) Enhance the modelling structure by including reserve provision capacities, the impact of transportation electrification on electricity demand, disaggregated demands in various sectors (industry, agriculture, and tertiary), storage technologies, and the biomass supply chain. (4) Incorporate new technologies such as intelligent vehicle charging and vehicle-to-grid strategies, demand-side management systems, internal hydrogen production, biofuels for transportation, emissions of pollutants other than CO₂, concentrated solar power plants, carbon capture and storage, and building insulation. (5) Assess the impact of optimal solutions on different actors. (6) Improve data collection through a crowd-source 	[149]

									and interdisciplinary development approach.		
Decarbonising the Alberta power system with carbon pricing	Alberta, Canada	Case study	This study investigates possible routes toward achieving a low-carbon power system in Alberta through a long-term, techno-economic optimization supply model. Simulations extend to 2060 and encompass scenarios that vary based on different carbon prices. The study assesses the resulting energy compositions, system expenses, and reductions in CO2 emissions, while also examining sensitivity to changes in fuel prices, technology costs, and electricity demand growth.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Some data is available at the article with Elsevier subscription [link]	Intrayear resolution: 36 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2010-2060	1 region	(1) Given that the most cost-effective emission reductions come from reducing coal-fired generation, policies targeting the retirement of coal could be a viable near-term alternative to carbon pricing. (2) While natural gas-fired generation alone cannot meet long-term emission targets without CCS, there is currently no apparent mid-term alternative for baseload generation. (3) An increase in the carbon price accelerates the deployment of wind and solar PV, and also leads to additional installations of Pulverised Coal-CCS. (4) CCS consistently emerges in scenario results as a low-carbon baseload generator that scales up electricity production as carbon policies strengthen. However, this role could potentially be assumed by another technology with comparable costs and performance, such as nuclear power, or by a future breakthrough technology yet to be developed.	(1) Explore the impacts of uncertainty in future costs and technology characteristics using alternative approaches like stochastic modelling. (2) Incorporate market characteristics into the system representation. (3) Evaluate the effects of climate change on future generator performance. (4) Explore interconnections and large-scale storage solutions, such as power-to-gas, as strategies to enhance the integration of variable renewables	[160]
An indicative analysis of investment opportunities in the African electricity supply sector - Using TEMBA (The Electricity Model Base for Africa)	Africa	Case study	This paper explores indicative scenarios of power plant investments focused on electricity trade potential. It utilizes OSeMOSYS, a cost-optimization tool for long-term energy planning, to develop least-cost system configurations. The study models electricity supply systems for forty-seven	Not applicable	Not applicable	Some data is available at the article with Elsevier subscription [link]	Intrayear resolution: 4 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2010-2050	47 regions	(1) There appears to be potential for both coordinated trade and national-focused power plant investments, alongside limited trade. Trade operates on two levels: firstly, increased transmission capacity has the potential to unlock power generation resources in one region,	(1) Conducting an explicit analysis of security and trade on a country-by-country basis. (2) Developing regional integrated GHG mitigation cost curves and exploring emissions trading. (3) Calculating power supply costs for individual countries and regions.	[97]

			countries individually and integrates them via trade links to create TEMBA (The Electricity Model Base for Africa).						thereby reducing system costs continent-wide. Secondly, as fuel costs decrease due to increased renewable energy technology (RET) penetration, there is potential to allocate domestic fossil fuel resources to other uses or for export. (2) The paper outlines indicative investments by country, including timing and average operational details. This information is valuable for targeting specific support mechanisms, such as power purchase agreements and joint infrastructure development for specific project sets.	(4) Understanding the impact of local or technology-specific constraints, such as hydro generation under changing climatic conditions. (5) Conducting in-depth analysis of potential intermittency and transmission constraints associated with increased deployment of renewable energy technologies (RET). (6) Incorporating greater temporal resolution, utilizing a larger number of time slices for analysis.	
An analysis of the power market in Saudi Arabia: Retrospective cost and environmental optimization	Saudi Arabia	Modelling	This paper presents an overview of the power sector in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA), incorporating the latest data. It applies a retrospective modeling approach to analyze the KSA power market between 2003 and 2013, focusing on (i) cost minimization and (ii) environmental impact minimization objectives. The analysis employs an enhanced version of the Open Source energy MOdelling SYStem (OSeMOSYS), considering both domestic and international fuel prices.	The implemented model improvements include: (a) efficiency adjustments to account for the typical temperature difference of 20–30 °C between winter and summer in arid countries, which significantly impacts power generation efficiency; (b) integration of a multi-objective target function that considers both costs and emissions to establish a Pareto frontier; and (c) assessment of emissions using the 'quality enhanced life days' (QELD) indicator, which concurrently	Mathematical modelling is available in the paper with Elsevier subscription [link] Code implementation is not available Code version: MathProg	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 6 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2003-2013	1 region	(1) Under a cost minimization objective without considering emission penalties, domestic fuel prices fail to drive energy efficiency or include renewables in the expansion plan, while international fuel prices are effective. (2) In cases aiming to minimize environmental impact, the results are nearly identical for both domestic and international fuel price scenarios, with cost having minimal influence on the expansion plan. (3) Expansion planning based on international fuel prices is costlier compared to domestic prices, which are heavily subsidized. (4) Surplus liquid fuel saved from local power generation could potentially be exported, bolstering KSA's global oil market share and	Incorporate water resources and forecast capacity additions for the next decade	[109]

				evaluates global emissions (e.g., carbon dioxide) and local emissions (e.g., NOx).					impacting international oil prices further.		
Supporting security and adequacy in future energy systems: The need to enhance long-term energy system models to better treat issues related to variability	Not applicable	Modelling	This study introduces an expanded functionality to the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) to address the impacts of short-term variability in supply and demand on system adequacy and security. Specifically, the study models system adequacy while increasing the share of wind energy and incorporates the modelling of operating reserve capacities needed for balancing services. The dynamics introduced by these model enhancements are demonstrated through an application case study.	Two main extensions were implemented in OSeMOSYS: i) Estimation of the capacity credit of wind power using a piece-wise linear approximation. ii) Capture of operating reserve requirements for short-term balancing (primary and secondary)	Mathematical modelling and code implementation are available in the supplementary material of the article with Wiley subscription [link] Code version: MathProg	Some data is available at the article with Wiley subscription [link]	Intrayear resolution: 8 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2010-2040	1 region	(1) Neglecting the impacts of variability in demand and generation on system adequacy and security may significantly underestimate the importance of flexibility within the power system. (2) Dispatchable power plants play a crucial role in ensuring the system's adequacy and security. However, markets may encounter a gap between the necessity for flexibility and the incentives to invest in flexible technologies. Improved modelling tools are needed for a comprehensive economic and technical evaluation of this gap.	(1) Expand the model to encompass a broader array of technological options, such as smart grids and interconnectors, to assess which improvements would most positively impact the system's flexibility. (2) Include flexibility options from other sectors, such as integrating electric vehicles in transportation or incorporating combined heat and power plants in the heating sector. (3) Enhance OSeMOSYS to incorporate modelling of elastic, price-dependent demands. (4) Conduct a more detailed analysis to account for input uncertainty and inter-year variations. (5) Evaluate the enhanced accuracy of the proof-of-concept presented in this paper through the use of a country-specific case study.	[150]
Estimating the cost of energy access: The case of the village of Suro Craic in Timor Leste	Timor Leste	Case study - Methodology	Building upon the WB (World Bank) Multi-Tier framework, this research provides estimates of the cost variations associated with achieving different tiers of electrification for a typical rural village in Timor Leste. The study combines this cost evaluation with a comparison of viable electrification alternatives for the region, including standalone systems, mini-grids, and grid connections	Not applicable	Not applicable	Some data is available at the article with Elsevier subscription [link] Other data can be made available under request.	Intrayear resolution: 18 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2010-2030	1 region	(1) Achieving a tier 5 of electricity access (based on World Bank definitions) for rural households between 2010 and 2030 could be up to seventy-five times more costly than achieving tier 1, and five times more costly than achieving tier 3 in the evaluated case study. (2) Grid connection becomes economically viable at higher tiers of energy access, contingent upon the cost of grid electricity in the country.	Develop additional case studies across diverse locations with varying socio-political dynamics	[79]

									(3) Investment in modern cooking firewood stoves could potentially decrease total costs due to the high opportunity cost of collecting fuelwood. However, this would necessitate initial capital investment for modern cook stoves. Additionally, transitioning to certain modern cooking fuels, such as LPG, would result in relatively modest increases in total costs over the evaluated period compared to open fire cooking solutions.		
Incorporating flexibility requirements into long-term energy system models - A case study on high levels of renewable electricity penetration in Ireland	Ireland	Case study - Methodology	This study explores an enhanced version of the open-source energy system model OSeMOSYS, designed to capture operating reserve and associated investment needs within a single tool. The impact of these model extensions is evaluated through a comparison with an Irish case study. The case study analyzed the effects of integrating a long-term energy system model (TIMES) with a unit commitment and dispatch model (PLEXOS).	Same modifications as in [150] Simplified version of hydropower storage modelling based on [152]	Mathematical modelling and code implementation are available in the appendix of the article with Elsevier subscription [link] Code version: MathProg	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 12 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2010-2050	1 region	Long-term energy models may significantly underestimate the importance of flexibility within the power system if short-term operating requirements are not taken into account. As a result, the energy strategies and policies derived from these models might underestimate the costs of achieving climate change or energy security targets. This oversight could lead to investments in a mix of technologies that fail to meet expected reliability standards and are not cost-optimal from a societal perspective.	Assessing the economic implications of market design and policies, particularly the potential benefits of sharing operating reserves across markets.	[153]
Modelling elements of Smart Grids e Enhancing the OSeMOSYS (Open Source Energy Modelling System) code (Additional – Outside bibliometric analysis)*	No country	Modelling	This paper expands on the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS), detailing how 'blocks of functionality' can be added to represent variability in electricity generation, prioritize demand types, shift demand, and include storage options. It demonstrates the flexibility and ease of use of	The OSeMOSYS code has been enhanced with four new features: i) Generation variability is now accounted for by adjusting the capacity factor parameter to higher temporal resolution from years to time slices.	Some mathematical modelling is explained at the article with Elsevier subscription [link] Code implementation is reported in an inexistent reference	Not available	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	1) Incorporate a detailed evaluation of various Smart Grid technologies using this energy modelling methodology. 2) Conduct comparative case studies to provide insights into the applicability of this approach relative to other methodologies. 3) Model how Smart Grid advancements might accelerate the delivery of	[152]

			<p>OSeMOSYS when modifying its code.</p>	<p>ii) Demand types can be prioritized, permitting some demand to go unmet if the supply cost exceeds a set threshold.</p> <p>iii) Demand shifting has been added, allowing final demand to be met earlier or later within a day within a defined timespan, with costs assigned for each timespan shift.</p> <p>iv) Energy storage modelling has been improved, enabling energy to be stored or discharged within a time slice, provided storage levels remain within specified minimum and maximum limits.</p>	Code version: MathProg					<p>essential energy services to the poor, such as assessing the social effectiveness of subsidies targeting specific services rather than electricity, or modelling trade-offs between low-cost tariffs and reduced reliability.</p> <p>4) Integrate intermittent and inflexible base load generation options into long-term energy system expansion plans.</p>	
LEAPs and Bounds-an Energy Demand and Constraint Optimised Model of the Irish Energy System	Ireland	Case study	<p>This paper introduces the first national-level model within the Long Range Energy Alternatives Planning (LEAP) software, integrating detailed end-use analysis on the demand side with a cost-minimizing optimization approach for electricity generation modelling. Through three scenarios spanning 2009–2020, the model evaluates the overall impact of various current and proposed energy efficiency policies on energy demand.</p>	Not applicable	Not applicable	<p>Some data is available at the article with Elsevier subscription [link]</p> <p>Other data can be made available under request.</p>	<p>Intrayear resolution: 104 timeslices</p> <p>Modelling horizon: 2009-2020</p>	1 region	<p>1. The policy measures with the highest potential for reducing energy consumption in the private car sector are non-technical, such as mileage reduction and modal shift. Without continued efforts to limit private car activity growth, the savings from energy efficiency measures will be mitigated.</p> <p>2. There are no policies or targets addressing the growing share of freight and aviation energy demand. Further policy focus should address these modes, especially freight transport, where efficiency and renewable energy options are possible.</p>	<p>1. Conduct additional scenarios on various policies outlined in the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP).</p> <p>2. Enhance the process of input data collection.</p> <p>3. Utilize European benchmarks and estimates for modelling energy demand in Ireland's industry and services sectors.</p>	[82]

									<p>3. To effectively realize savings potential in the residential sector, government policy needs to address both the number of dwellings undergoing retrofits and the depth of retrofit works carried out.</p> <p>4. Irish energy policy would benefit from explicitly acknowledging the uncertainties of energy efficiency policies upfront. Using a framework like LEAP to quantify that uncertainty would encourage more diligent policy management.</p>		
Assessing the Impact of Applying Individual Discount Rates in Power System Expansion of Ecuador Using OSeMOSYS	Ecuador	Modelling	This study employs an open-source model generator to develop the first long-term capacity expansion model for Ecuador. We select specific social and hurdle rates to represent the government's decision to mobilize private energy infrastructure investments. Various scenarios for social and hurdle rates are constructed to evaluate the sensitivity of renewable and conventional generation technologies to these rates.	A new feature has been added to the OSeMOSYS code to apply different discount rates for each technology. This update allows the modeler to utilize both a global discount or social discount rate (SDR) and specific hurdle rates. The corresponding equations have been modified to incorporate the new discount rate parameter. Additionally, a new parameter called PvAnnuity has been implemented to calculate the present value of the investment cost for each technology when using specific discount rates.	Mathematical modelling is available at the article [link] Code implementation is available at [link] Code version: MathProg	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 72 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2003-2013	1 region	<p>1) Hydropower is chosen as the generation technology in the country from a cost-minimization perspective, without considering climate uncertainty. If the government plans to fund future medium and large hydro projects through private utilities, they will need to address contentious social and environmental constraints experienced in the past.</p> <p>2) Clean funding mechanisms and public incentives are essential to make new non-hydro renewable energy sources financially and economically viable.</p>	Define hurdle rates specifically for the energy sector in the LAC region	[27]
Soft-linking bottom-up energy models with top-down input-output models to	Egypt	Case study - Methodology	This paper has two main objectives: first, it presents a new method for integrating bottom-up	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 15 timeslices	1 region	1) Reducing GHG emissions from the electricity generation mix alone is insufficient to	Not available	[125]

assess the environmental impact of future energy scenarios			energy optimization models with linear top-down Input-Output macroeconomic models. Second, this approach is applied to the Egyptian economy to evaluate the economic and environmental impacts of changes in the electricity production mix in future energy scenarios (2015-2040).				Modelling horizon: 2015-2040		achieve the projected nationwide GHG emissions targets for 2040. 2) The potential for GHG emissions reductions diminishes over time throughout the planning period, even as the share of renewables continues to grow. 3) Significant GHG emissions reductions have occurred in the early years of the planning period. Therefore, policymakers should identify the optimal timing for directing investments towards enhancing the efficiency of the industrial, services, and transportation sectors, rather than solely focusing on increasing renewable capacity, which also necessitates additional investments in electricity transmission and distribution infrastructure.		
Modeling the long-term evolution of the Italian power sector: The role of renewable resources and energy storage facilities	Italy	Case study	The objective of this study is to develop a model for the Italian power sector, focusing on long-term planning from 2021 to 2050, utilizing an updated version of OSeMOSYS that incorporates time series clustering. The model assesses the potential for photovoltaic and onshore wind technologies to evaluate their actual expandability. Additionally, both batteries and hydrogen are included as electrical energy storage systems. The study then investigates the role of variable renewable energy sources (VRES) and storage facilities (batteries and hydrogen) in facilitating the gradual decarbonization of	Modified code based on [138]	Available at link	Some data is available in the supplementary material of the article link	Intrayear resolution: Sensitivity analysis from 30 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2021-2050	1 region	1) This analysis underscores the critical role of energy storage facilities in supporting energy systems that heavily rely on variable renewable energy sources (VRES). Specifically, battery storage emerges as the preferred solution during the initial phase of the power sector transition, owing to its lower investment costs and higher efficiency compared to hydrogen storage. As the penetration of VRES increases over time, hydrogen storage becomes essential due to its economic advantages as a long-term storage	1) Expand this analysis to include other sectors such as heating, transportation, and industry. 2) Investigate energy interactions with neighbouring countries to identify more cost-effective solutions for the future Italian power sector.	[51]

			the Italian power sector from both economic and environmental perspectives.						option, despite having lower round-trip efficiency than batteries. 2) A significant share of VRES in the power system results in a substantial reduction in CO2 emissions throughout the modelling period. Notably, these outcomes were achieved without any decarbonization measures (such as CO2 constraints) and are attributed to the anticipated decline in costs for VRES and storage technologies in the future.		
Integrated climate, land, energy, and water framework to support the Nationally Determined Contribution updating process	Costa Rica	Case study	This paper outlines the framework used to develop the Climate, Land, Energy, and Water CLEW-CR model, detailing the processes from data collection to scenario creation and cost-benefit analysis. It also describes how the model has been utilized to align the country's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) with its National Development Plan (NDP). More than 15 different scenarios were generated to inform the country's discussions during the NDC updating process, highlighting the model's flexibility in addressing various policy questions.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 2 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2050	1 region	1) There is a need for policies that promote technological advancements and infrastructure development for electric vehicles and renewable energy. 2) Policy measures should extend to legislation and improve monitoring to prevent illegal activities affecting forest areas while encouraging sustainable agricultural practices. 3) Policies in the water sector should prioritize the expansion of wastewater treatment facilities and the implementation of efficient waste management practices. 4) Fostering stakeholder engagement, establishing public-private partnerships, and investing in essential infrastructure and technology are vital for effective sector-specific policies. Additionally, enhancing monitoring and enforcement for forest protection and	1) Conduct additional technical analyses, particularly regarding grid expansion and financing. 2) Provide details on how the industrial sector will reduce emissions and how its strategies can be better aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals.	[91]

									sustainable land use, along with providing financial incentives for sustainable practices, is crucial.		
Analyses of optimum generation scenarios for sustainable power generation in Ghana	Ghana	Case study	This study analyzes optimal generation scenarios for Ghana from 2010 to 2040. The Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS), an optimization model for long-term energy planning integrated into the Long-range Energy Alternatives Planning (LEAP) tool, was used to model the generation system. The model was applied to the reference scenario (OPT), which explores the least-cost development of the system without any policy changes. Three groups of policy scenarios were developed based on potential future energy policy directions in Ghana: energy emission targets, carbon taxes, and improvements in transmission and distribution losses.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 2 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2010-2040	1 region	1) Implementing carbon minimization policies will encourage diversification of the generation mix, leading to a greater penetration of renewable energy technologies and a reduction in overall fossil fuel generation in Ghana. 2) Significant savings in greenhouse gas emissions are achieved through improvements in transmission and distribution losses, resulting in net benefits from avoided emissions compared to the base case. 3) The adoption of strategies to reduce transmission and distribution losses, alongside carbon minimization policies like emission targets and carbon taxes, will foster the development of a more efficient, reliable, and environmentally friendly energy system in Ghana.	Evaluate the impact of high penetration of renewable energy generation technologies on grid stability, along with conducting grid expansion studies to accommodate potential future generation growth.	[108]
Analyzing carbon emissions policies for the Bolivian electric sector	Bolivia	Case study	The energy system optimization modeling framework OSeMOSYS is employed to examine pathways for the power sector's transition. Techno-economic characteristics and policies are integrated to create bracketing scenarios for the future energy system, comparing a business-as-usual approach with a scenario featuring ambitious renewable energy policies.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 36 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2010-2060	1 region	1) Easily achievable measures, such as adhering to the current electric system development plan and prohibiting large hydropower projects in the Amazon, would have only a short-term impact on the system. 2) If all proposed policies were implemented, there would be a significant reduction in carbon emissions followed by stabilization. However, this reduction and the participation of natural	1) Improve the spatial and temporal resolution of the system modelling. 2) Integrate energy storage into the modelling framework. 3) Account for emissions from large hydropower projects. 4) Assess demand-side management policies. 5) Include additional sectors in a comprehensive energy system model, such as a more detailed analysis of energy consumption in the industry and mining sectors, a broader range of	[157]

									gas thermal plants are constrained by the maximum available capacity of geothermal, biomass, and medium-sized hydroelectric sources. 3) The transformation will require focusing on: 1) reducing the artificial competitiveness of thermal power plants (through subsidies), 2) banning high-impact power plants (primarily large hydropower), and 3) establishing clear long-term objectives for renewable energy participation in the system, aligned with the goals of current short-term plans.	residential energy sources (including direct combustion), and, importantly, incorporate transportation as a major energy-consuming sector.	
The role of energy efficiency in the management of water resources of the syrdarya river basin	No access to the article	No access to the article	No access to the article	No access to the article	No access to the article	No access to the article	No access to the article	No access to the article	No access to the article	No access to the article	No access to the article
Assessing the effects of energy efficiency and different tariff policies on energy mix for decarbonization	Not applicable	Case study	This work aims to evaluate the effects of various energy policies designed to promote decarbonization by increasing the use of renewable sources. Specifically, it examines the implementation of energy efficiency policies and the application of hourly differential electricity tariffs. The Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) is used to visualize the impacts of these actions in the short, medium, and long term, from 2024 to 2046.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 6 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2024-2046	1 region	1) Applying hourly differential tariffs has negligible effects compared to a flat tariff, except for increasing reliance on fossil fuels. 2) Differential tariffs do not reduce the need for generation capacity, and consequently, do not lower investment and maintenance costs. This is likely because demand shifts to hours with less solar power, necessitating a system for both day and night or storage solutions. 3) Implementing energy efficiency policies offers a promising opportunity for decarbonization by increasing the share of renewable energy.	1) Conduct a more detailed assessment of the impact on transmission and distribution networks. 2) Accurately calculate peak demand hours to ensure the viability of renewable energy increases in conjunction with differential tariffing. 3) Assess the stabilization requirements resulting from the higher shares of renewable energy.	[66]
A Nexus-Based Impact Assessment of Rapid Transitions	Greece	Case study - Methodology	This paper investigates the various impacts of swiftly decarbonizing the Greek	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 24 timeslices	1 region	1) Rapid decarbonization of the power sector can significantly lower carbon	1) Integrate other sectors of the energy system to	[126]

of the Power Sector: The Case of Greece			power sector by 2035, particularly at the local level. The study evaluates the cost-optimal power mix, power costs, land use, biomass utilization, GDP, and employment. To achieve this, a technology-rich cost optimization model representing Greece's power sector is connected to a global Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) macroeconomic model, which focuses on the Greek economy.				Modelling horizon: 2023-2035		emissions from power generation and reduce the risk of harming ecosystems and biodiversity. 2) Short- and medium-term power generation costs could decrease due to reduced reliance on fossil fuels, which have highly variable operational costs. 3) Although rapid decarbonization may increase land use competition, this can be managed with careful planning to mitigate adverse impacts on biodiversity and socially significant scenic areas, considering the modest scale of land required relative to Greece's total land area. 4) Wind and solar technologies can be the primary drivers of the rapid decarbonization process in the power sector. 5) Lower power generation costs can enhance household disposable income and final demand, boosting economic activity as measured by GDP. Additionally, this transition could create additional jobs annually from 2023 to 2035 in the Greek economy.	examine interactions with the power sector. 2) Apply multi-objective optimization, incorporating specific constraints beyond system costs, such as land use, into the optimization model. 3) Include critical material demand as an evaluation criterion for power system transformation pathways. 4) Conduct a comprehensive examination of land use requirements, such as applying sensitivity analyses to account for variability in land factors for each technology or increasing the spatial resolution of the analysis using Geographic Information Systems (GIS).	
Is there a case for a coal moratorium in Indonesia? Power sector optimization modeling of low-carbon strategies	Indonesia	Case study	This study employs the LEAP software as a forecasting model alongside the OSeMOSYS energy optimization tool to evaluate options and changes in Indonesia's power sector up to 2050. The research focuses on two primary questions: identifying the least-cost strategies to meet	Not applicable	Not applicable	Some data is available at the article [link]	Intrayear resolution: 16 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2021-2050	1 region	1) Decision-making towards achieving a low-carbon economy involves navigating the delicate balance among cost implications, energy security, and CO2 emissions reduction. 2) Implementing carbon taxation could create a revenue stream, despite	1) Assess the significance of each key indicator (costs, energy security, and CO2 emissions reduction) in policy design. 2) Evaluate the appropriate level of carbon taxation to facilitate a low-carbon transition. 3) Include provincial jurisdictional data on power	[69]

			projected electricity demand with a priority on minimizing coal use and deriving policy insights to support a low-carbon electricity supply in Indonesia.						only partially internalizing emissions reduction. 3) The ambitious net-zero emissions target poses uncertainties. Achieving this goal could potentially exhaust Indonesia's renewable energy potential, leading to heavy dependence on solar energy as the primary renewable resource beyond 2050.	generation and consumption.	
Enhancing decarbonization of power generation through electricity trade in the Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East Region	Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East Region	Case study	This study aims to demonstrate the potential benefits of enhancing electricity trade between EMME countries, which could unlock the region's untapped renewable energy resources. A model representing the national electricity supply systems of seventeen EMME countries is developed using the cost-optimization framework (OSeMOSYS). This model projects cost-optimal development pathways by evaluating scenarios with varying levels of regional trade. The comparison of these scenarios quantifies the implications for renewable energy deployment, greenhouse gas emissions, and overall system costs.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 66 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2021-2050	17 regions	1) Although electricity trade across the EMME region may not significantly impact renewable energy deployment without high climate ambition, it can facilitate the cost-optimal achievement of international greenhouse gas emission targets. 2) Complementing national energy and climate plans with regional cooperation can promote coordinated efforts that leverage electricity trade potential, aiding future revisions of NDC submissions. 3) Regional cooperation in identifying cost-effective grid interconnection projects can unlock significant renewable energy potential, supporting further investments in generation, storage, and grid network capacity. 4) Renewable energy investments are expected to rise across the EMME region in all scenarios, improving energy security for countries like Cyprus, Greece, Jordan, Lebanon, and Palestine that currently depend on energy imports. However, this deployment must be accompanied by	1) Conduct a sensitivity analysis by varying key assumptions. 2) Soft-link the technoeconomic model with macroeconomic models to gain socioeconomic insights, such as impacts on employment and economic growth. 3) Involve local stakeholders and input from national authorities. 4) Expand the model to include the broader energy system (e.g., transport, heating, and cooling) and other energy vectors. 5) Endogenize demand projections by considering the effects of climate change on long-term demand for cooling and heating, and the generation output of renewable technologies like solar PV, wind, and hydropower. 6) Study the potential for renewable electricity exports from the EMME region to continental Europe, including the export electricity price at which this option becomes attractive. 7) Develop the model to include hydrogen production via electrolysis, allowing the assessment of a scenario where green	[61]

									<p>investments in storage technologies and supported by grid interconnections. Proper policies and regulations are needed to promote private investments alongside physical infrastructure.</p> <p>5) A favorable regulatory framework should be established to develop regional or subregional power pools for electricity exchange within the EMME region and potential exports to continental Europe.</p>	<p>hydrogen can be exported from the EMME region.</p> <p>8) Assess the extended role of nuclear energy in achieving decarbonization in the EMME region.</p>	
<p>A stakeholder-informed modelling study of Greece's energy transition amidst an energy crisis: The role of natural gas and climate ambition</p>	Greece	Case study - Methodology	<p>This study evaluates the trajectory of Greece's electricity mix and its dependence on natural gas under two scenarios: the current policy framework and an ambitious scenario aiming for full decarbonization by 2035. We utilize an energy system modeling framework, incorporating LEAP and OSeMOSYS models for Greece, and employ a stakeholder-informed fuzzy cognitive mapping exercise to identify transition uncertainties.</p>	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	<p>Intrayear resolution: Unknown</p> <p>Modelling horizon: 2019-2050</p>	1 region	<p>1) Policy responses to the energy crisis that favor a diverse mix of renewable energy sources over a reliance on natural gas can lead to a cleaner and more economical energy system.</p> <p>2) Although a varied energy mix can mitigate uncertainties, this approach requires slightly higher investments due to the inclusion of less cost-effective technologies.</p> <p>3) Despite the uncertainties surrounding fossil fuel prices and the growth/availability of electricity capacity, Greece can pursue ambitious climate goals cost-optimally, potentially eliminating the need for natural gas equivalent to current Russian imports as early as 2026.</p> <p>4) Stakeholders highlighted the risk of fossil-fuel lock-in, suggesting that governments should prioritize long-term goals and leverage the current momentum to establish clear policies for effective</p>	<p>1) Establish bidirectional links between OSeMOSYS and LEAP to capture the impact of rising electricity prices on energy demand, as households may reduce consumption to avoid higher costs, even at the risk of energy poverty.</p> <p>2) Analyze the expansion of electricity storage as well as transmission and distribution grids.</p> <p>3) Explore significant demand-side investments needed for high EV penetration and improved energy efficiency, considering behavioral changes and modal shifts.</p> <p>4) Study the spatial constraints for hydropower.</p> <p>5) Incorporate a broader mix of mitigation technologies, including the generation capacity of green hydrogen and its impact on transport energy demand.</p>	[116]

									mitigation and accelerated transition.		
Global sensitivity analysis to enhance the transparency and rigour of energy system optimisation modelling	Global	Methodology	This paper offers detailed guidelines for performing a global sensitivity analysis of an Energy System Optimization Model (ESOM), aiming to overcome barriers to adopting this approach. With a pedagogical focus, the paper begins by discussing the importance of conducting a global sensitivity analysis. It then explains how to implement such an analysis using the Morris method within an ESOM, demonstrated through a series of simple illustrative models built using the Open Source energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) framework, followed by a realistic example.	Same as [106]	Code is available at [link]	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: Up to 288 timeslices Maximum modelling horizon: 2015-2100	Up to 265 nodes (global coverage)	Not applicable	Not available	[110]
Modelling a Decarbonization Agenda for Bembibre's Industrial Park	Bembibre industrial zone in the Bierzo region, Spain	Case study	This paper outlines the development of the Sustainable Strategy Agenda for the Bembibre industrial zone in the Bierzo region using the Open-Source Energy Modeling System (OSeMOSYS). Various roadmaps were assessed to aid decision-making, including repurposing an old coal mine galley into a reverse hydro storage system, establishing enterprises focused on recycling solar panels, and integrating second-life batteries from electric vehicles as energy storage solutions.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: Unknown Modelling horizon: 2022-2035	1 region	1) Economically and locally, the most promising option is a mix of reverse hydro storage and reconditioned second-life batteries. This combination reduces reliance on external green network technology, ensuring local production meets almost all demand. 2) Significant social impacts are anticipated, including the creation of new jobs during both the implementation and exploitation phases.	Not available	[105]
Long-term optimization model for the Gambia's energy transition	Gambia	Case study	This paper investigates the optimal capacity expansion planning for the period 2020-2050 using the Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS). It considers three scenarios: the Business as Usual (BAU) scenario, which	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: Unknown Modelling horizon: 2020-2050	1 region	1) The scenario that enables significant decarbonization by 2050 also comes with the highest cost, suggesting the necessity for sustainable financing solutions to support this transition.	1) Improve the accuracy of energy demand projections. 2) Explore potential financing mechanisms to support The Gambia's transition to sustainable energy.	[73]

			continues the current power generation pattern; a scenario aligned with Gambia's strategic electricity roadmap (2021-2040); and a third scenario focused on high renewable energy penetration in the energy mix.						<p>2) Achieving the energy transition will require diverse strategies that integrate various technologies and capitalize on local resources, particularly solar energy, which is plentiful throughout the year but currently not part of the country's energy mix.</p> <p>3) The limited solar capacity in the government's plans fails to decrease The Gambia's reliance on external energy sources, leaving the energy system vulnerable. It is more economically feasible to increase the use of locally available energy resources.</p> <p>4) The energy transition may prove economically advantageous over time due to the absence of fuel costs in renewable energy technologies. Additionally, from a social standpoint, it offers significant job creation potential, considering the new capacity required.</p>		
Mid- to long-term capacity planning for a reliable power system in Kenya	Kenya	Case study - Methodology	This study introduces a new framework that integrates OSeMOSYS, a capacity expansion model (CEM), with FlexTool, a production cost model (PCM), to better represent variable renewable energy sources. This approach is used to evaluate how Kenya can meet its increasing energy demand while maintaining its goal of achieving a fully renewable energy system.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 48 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2019-2050	1 region	<p>1) Kenya is positioned to maintain its low carbon generation system while meeting future demand growth, leveraging its substantial wind and geothermal resources. Geothermal energy is expected to provide firm generation capacity, supplemented by increased storage, to manage the variability of an expanded wind capacity.</p> <p>2) Kenya will continue assessing wind resources to produce detailed wind mapping, identify promising areas for wind</p>	<p>1) Expand the procedure to cover more key years, starting with 2040.</p> <p>2) Apply regional disaggregation to both models.</p> <p>3) Explore additional flexibility sources, including demand response.</p> <p>4) Perform a comprehensive evaluation of the reserve margin levels.</p> <p>5) Evaluate the effects of climate change on hydropower generation.</p> <p>6) Incorporate geospatial data on renewable resources.</p>	[112]

									energy development, facilitate investments in large-scale projects, and support informed decision-making for both public and private sector deployment of wind resources. Additionally, the development of a Renewable Energy Auction Policy is aimed at attracting private sector investments in renewable energy generation, diversifying national power sources, and enhancing energy security. 3) As Kenya aims to sustain a high renewables system, ensuring system flexibility will be crucial for maintaining a reliable supply as demand grows. This analysis underscores the importance of planning tools that adequately consider flexibility requirements to avoid suboptimal investment decisions.	7) Develop methods to address modelling uncertainty.	
Analyses of Optimum Production Scenarios for Sustainable Power Production in Morocco	Morocco	Case study	This study evaluates the impact of CO2 emission constraints on the Moroccan electricity mix. Using the OSeMOSYS tool, we assessed Morocco's current production growth plan and analyzed alternative scenarios to highlight the impact of different production systems on emissions. The study aims to demonstrate how a carbon tax and emission cap contribute to the development of renewable energy sources in the electricity mix.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: Unknown Modelling horizon: 2015-2050	1 region	1) Setting an emission reduction target and implementing a carbon tax will significantly enhance the diversification of Morocco's electricity mix by introducing renewable energy as a cost-effective and sustainable option. This shift will reduce the country's reliance on fossil fuels, which are prone to supply disruptions and price fluctuations, thereby improving energy reliability. 2) A carbon tax leads to greater diversification of the electricity mix and a more substantial reduction in emissions compared to an emission	1) Analyze the interactions between the power system and other economic sectors. 2) Study the economic benefits of renewable energies by exploring scenarios involving fuel price fluctuations, assumptions on technology costs, and improved transmission and distribution efficiency.	[31]

									target. This is due to the internalization of emission costs, which directly affects the costs of conventional technologies. The study suggests that a carbon tax would be an effective instrument to accelerate decarbonization, with the tax revenues being used to finance clean energy projects.		
The role of energy-water nexus to motivate transboundary cooperation: An indicative analysis of the Drina river basin	Drina River Basin, South-East Europe	Case study	This paper examines integrated energy and water solutions to encourage transboundary cooperation in operating hydropower plants (HPPs) in the Drina River Basin (DRB) in South-East Europe. The Open Source Energy Modeling System (OSeMOSYS) was utilized to create a multi-country model that includes a simplified hydrological system representing the cascade of HPPs in the DRB, alongside other electricity options, such as energy efficiency measures.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Some data is available in the Appendix [link]	Intrayear resolution: 36 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2010-2035	3 regions	1) Enhanced cooperation in the operation of hydropower plants along the Drina River Basin could increase annual production downstream without negatively impacting upstream output. Besides improving the legislative framework to support coordinated operations, developing information exchange systems among power plants along the river and across national borders would be advantageous. 2) If coordination is formalized, the benefits of cooperation could be amplified through development plans and investments in the electricity transmission network. The analysis indicates that increased hydroelectric production could unlock potential for international trade within and beyond the three riparian countries. 3) Energy efficiency measures reduce the pressure on primary resources for energy supply (primarily hydro and coal), while improved cooperation in hydropower plant operations further enhances production. This could lead to	1) Develop a variable and volatile monthly water flow scheme to better evaluate the system's resilience against future weather volatility, including an overall drying climate and climate change-induced drought and flood peaks. 2) Provide detailed guidance for the hourly scheduling of hydropower plants by integrating the OSeMOSYS energy system model with a specialized hydrological system model or an hourly dispatch model. 3) Examine the effects of power plant discharge on the temperature of the rivers. 4) Collect additional data from local institutions and electricity utility companies, focusing on site-specific technology costs and water availability data.	[94]

									increased water availability for non-energy uses, such as agriculture. Additionally, these benefits contribute to reduced GHG emissions, aiding the countries in meeting their NDCs.		
Assessment of optimal pathways for power generation system in Ghana	Ghana	Case study	This study employs the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS), integrated with the Long-range Energy Alternatives Planning (LEAP) tool, to optimize long-term energy planning in Ghana. The research aims to develop optimal generation pathways and dispatch schedules for various power generation technologies. By simulating both conventional and renewable energy technologies, the study assesses the technological, economic, and environmental impacts of renewable energy policies from 2010 to 2040.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: Unknown Modelling horizon: 2010-2040	1 region	1) Implementing comprehensive policies to reduce transmission and distribution losses and enhance energy efficiency in Ghana will lead to a notable decrease in both demand and greenhouse gas emissions. These policies will also encourage a more diverse generation mix, increasing the share of renewable energy technologies. 2) Fossil fuel-based generation will remain a crucial component of Ghana's energy system, as renewable technologies alone will not meet all future energy demands. 3) Gradually phasing out electricity subsidies will make Non-Conventional Renewable Energy Technologies (NRET) more economically viable. This process should be gradual and aligned with the expansion of NRET to ensure a smooth transition.	Examine how a high integration of renewable energy generation technologies affects grid stability.	[120]
Techno-economic comparison of centralized and distributed power generation to support large-scale transport electrification in Costa Rica	Costa Rica	Case study - Methodology	This paper presents a methodology that integrates a bottom-up long-term energy system model with deep-uncertainty analysis to evaluate the future average electricity price for two contrasting systems: one based on utility-scale projects and the other on distributed generation.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not available	Intrayear resolution: 2 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2022-2050	1 region	1) A highly distributed system experiences fewer electrical losses but requires higher installed capacity compared to utility-scale systems. This is because distributed solar PV technology has lower capacity factors than wind generation, which is the predominant	1) Investigate the trade-offs of battery degradation with vehicle-to-grid (V2G) technology for any decarbonization scenario. 2) Examine the operational aspects of the power grid and other energy demands, especially in regions where resource availability is more variable.	[130]

			<p>Additionally, it assesses how these prices impact the financial benefits for energy sector investors and transport users stemming from transport electrification. This methodology is applied to Costa Rica's transport electrification goals, a middle-income country with substantial renewable generation capacity and commitments to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050.</p>						<p>source for incumbent firms.</p> <p>2) There is significant potential to increase the use of Costa Rica's existing centralized infrastructure, particularly the capacity factors of hydropower and large-scale wind projects.</p> <p>3) Transport users will benefit from low electricity prices due to the low unit costs of generation technologies and other electrical infrastructure. However, the economic feasibility of distributed generation (DG) systems depends on the costs of storage and other necessary equipment; higher costs make DG less competitive compared to centralized systems.</p> <p>4) The discount rate significantly influences price and benefit metrics. Lower discount rates lead to reduced costs and increased benefits and revenues. Derisking renewable energy investments in middle-income economies like Costa Rica can maximize the positive impacts of transport electrification.</p> <p>5) Lowering the cost of renewable energy while increasing installed capacity presents an international challenge that countries must address to achieve lower electricity prices.</p> <p>6) Policymakers should enhance the visibility of future power sector impacts, particularly the interplay between the power sector and</p>	<p>3) Consider geographical dimensions in energy supply: some areas, such as rural regions, may find distributed generation more cost-effective than centralized systems due to the high costs of long interconnections.</p> <p>4) Evaluate how effective electric vehicle charging management can lower storage investment requirements, contributing to more affordable electricity.</p>	
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									transport EV penetration, as a means to advance economic development, climate, and energy security objectives.		
Policy options to mitigate the fiscal impact of road transport decarbonization: Application to Costa Rica	Costa Rica	Case study - Methodology	This study develops a method to assess options for maintaining fiscal revenues without hindering the decarbonization benefits for firms and households. Using a long-term energy system model, it estimates the financial impact of transport decarbonization on the government, firms (including buses, taxis, freight, and other private uses), and households, categorized by income level and region of residence. It then evaluates how the government can utilize energy, property, import, and distance-based tax adjustments to offset the fiscal cost of decarbonization and analyzes the incidence of these adjustments on firms and households.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Data will be made available on request	Intrayear resolution: 2 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2018-2050	1 region	<p>1) Decarbonizing road transport in Costa Rica, according to its National Decarbonization Plan, will reduce tax revenue from vehicle imports, property taxes, and fuel consumption under current tax rules. However, the plan's financial benefits will surpass the tax revenue loss compared to a business-as-usual (BAU) scenario.</p> <p>2) Costa Rica and similar governments can reform their tax structures to redistribute benefits, eliminating negative fiscal impacts while achieving environmental and economic development goals.</p> <p>3) Governments should identify the optimal timing for tax reforms within their road transport decarbonization plans.</p> <p>4) Implementing a mix of tax options spreads costs across various stakeholders and results in moderate tax rate increases. Citizens are likely to accept a reasonable tax rate hike if their overall transport costs decrease, benefiting from decarbonization.</p> <p>5) Adjustments to tax structures will be necessary once integrated decarbonization policies start eroding the carbon tax base.</p>	1) Assess the financial impact of road transport decarbonization on households, firms, and government revenues, considering uncertainties like fuel and technology costs and transport demand, identifying the trade-offs governments might encounter when deciding on tax enforcement based on these uncertainties. 2) Analyze the endogenous tax effects using quantitative techniques to understand how tax changes impact incentives, such as whether taxing electricity in the short term discourages the purchase of electric vehicles. 3) Broaden the analysis to include other countries with car manufacturing industries and oil extraction sectors	[131]

<p>Identifying cross-sectoral policy synergies for decarbonization: towards short-lived climate pollutant mitigation action in Costa Rica</p>	<p>Costa Rica</p>	<p>Case study - Methodology</p>	<p>This paper estimates the black carbon and methane emission mitigation potential of the National Decarbonization Plan (NDP) by analyzing stated measures. Using established long-term energy and land-use planning tools adapted for estimating short-lived climate pollutants (SLCPs), we assess the impact of NDP mitigation measures on the value chains of transport, industry, solid waste, and livestock activities. We extract instruments from existing policy documents and examine the activities required to bring goods or services from inception to use through a value chain analysis. Additionally, we consult stakeholders to identify implementation barriers for these instruments and score them based on their potential for cross-sectoral synergy.</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>Data will be made available on request</p>	<p>Intrayear resolution: 2 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2018-2050</p>	<p>1 region</p>	<p>1) Public policy should prioritize tools that promote mitigation across multiple sectors, creating cross-sectoral synergies. For example, updating urban and municipal regulatory plans to incorporate public transport, freight, and waste management can achieve these synergies. 2) Costa Rica will need to collaborate with neighboring countries to develop complementary strategies, including transnational governance, technology innovation (new products from R&D), market demand for new products, technology transfer and financial flows, carbon pricing, and carbon markets. 3) Analyzing methane emissions highlights the significant role of consumer behavior in mitigation, such as reducing food waste and minimizing landfill pressure. 4) Although public-private partnerships are appealing for financing low-carbon technology adoption, they can expose countries to vulnerabilities in the event of climate disasters. In such cases, the government may need to use fiscal resources to compensate private partners. 5) Countries should integrate long-term climate adaptation strategies into their short-term plans to ensure cohesive policy development.</p>	<p>1) Validate the instrument analysis through broader expert participation. 2) Study climate policy integration mechanisms, co-responsibility of actors, and the interconnectedness between actors. 3) Model and assess hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs) to develop more comprehensive mitigation strategies.</p>	<p>[92]</p>
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<p>The Bigger Picture: Robust Decarbonization of the Transport Sector in Costa Rica</p>	<p>Costa Rica</p>	<p>Case study - Methodology</p>	<p>This article outlines the process undertaken to develop the decarbonization pathway for Costa Rica's transport and energy sectors, as detailed in the country's National Decarbonization Plan (NDP). We describe the involvement of stakeholders in the design of the energy system model and its subsequent use to create scenarios that map out transformations toward mid-century goals. The development of the integrated energy system model is presented to examine the coupling between the electricity and transport sectors, alongside a discussion of key policies aimed at decarbonizing transport. Additionally, we analyze the importance of considering long-term uncertainties in the scenarios to identify potential risks and preempt negative outcomes. Finally, we highlight the challenges facing the decarbonization of the transport sector, aiming to raise awareness and preparedness among other countries.</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>Not available</p>	<p>Intrayear resolution: 2 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2020-2050</p>	<p>1 region</p>	<p>1) Organizing workshops or bilateral meetings with various stakeholders can reveal perspectives that energy experts might overlook, such as the impact of decarbonization on revenue. 2) Energy policies must identify development opportunities for national actors. 3) Modelling and energy policy targets must be transparent. 4) Energy modelling efforts should enhance the understanding of measures required to achieve transformations, linking them to country-specific opportunities that boost competitiveness. 5) Institutions responsible for implementing energy policy should maintain continuous stakeholder engagement, supported by rigorous techno-economic analysis.</p>	<p>Producing quantitative insights for specific actions based on strategic plans. For example, this can include financing levels for targeted transport demand management investments.</p>	<p>[86]</p>
<p>Exploring European decarbonisation pathways in the Power Decisions Game</p>	<p>Europe</p>	<p>Modelling</p>	<p>This paper introduces a Power Decisions Game designed to explore the dynamics and insights gained from analyzing the impact of policy decisions using a power system optimization model as an engagement tool. It enables non-energy analysts, including policymakers, academics, and the interested public, to examine the effects of selected policy and investment choices on the European power system. Specifically, the game</p>	<p>Include a Python package called OSeMOSYS_step to enable myopic foresight. This package allows users to run a model while considering potential decisions at specific decision points. It divides the modelling period into a series of consecutive steps. The first step spans six years,</p>	<p>Code is available at [link] Code version: MathProg</p>	<p>Available at [link]</p>	<p>Intrayear resolution: 15 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2050</p>	<p>30 regions</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>1) Enhance the game interface by incorporating additional model indicators. 2) Expand the scope to cover more sectors of the energy system. 3) Add a multi-player mode option. 4) Upgrade the OSeMOSYS_step package to fully leverage high-performance computing infrastructure. 5) Develop functionality to offer decision options that depend on previous choices. For instance, if the</p>	<p>[133]</p>

			investigates how decisions regarding the pace of emission reductions, the adoption of carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies, biomass imports, and the expansion of cross-border electricity transmission lines influence accumulated emissions per capita, required investments, and the levelized cost of electricity.	and each subsequent step is ten years long. Between steps, new data can be incorporated to create alternative scenarios related to decisions or new technological developments. Residual capacities are derived from the results of the previous step and the original model data, while all other data are provided from the initial model.						emission limit is zero, it could remove options for emission reduction speeds.	
Modeling a 100% renewable energy pathway in developing Countries: A case study of State of Goa, India	Goa, India	Case study	The study introduces an innovative approach to renewable energy research and development, providing a detailed analysis customized to the Goa state's unique characteristics. It emphasizes temporal resolution to account for resource variability, formulates targeted strategies for 100% renewable energy deployment, and employs open-source models for transparent and accessible energy planning. Additionally, stakeholder engagement ensures alignment with local needs and priorities, promoting inclusive decision-making essential for successful renewable energy transitions in the state.	Same as [115]	Same as [115]	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 12, 72, 144 and 288 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2020-2050	1 region	1) For Goa to transition to renewable energy, options include utilizing green electricity from both local generation and imports. Key policy measures to support this shift are Renewable Purchase Obligations (RPOs) and long-term Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs), which could incentivize hybrid systems with battery storage. Additionally, the state could benefit from collaborating with renewable-rich states to allocate capacity and install renewable energy systems. 2) To cut final energy consumption and achieve universal clean cooking in Goa by 2050, the adoption of modern technologies such as biogas and electric cooking is crucial. 3) Electrifying two-wheelers, three-wheelers, cars, buses, and taxis can reduce emissions and	Enhancing energy models by integrating land use factors—such as the land area designated for solar parks and wind farms in other states, and land allocated for biomass in Goa—using Climate Land Energy Water (CLEWs) analysis.	[118]

									energy consumption by 2050. However, challenges such as battery costs and the need for charging infrastructure must be addressed.		
A dataset for energy demand and supply modelling in Sierra Leone	Sierra Leone	Data article	This article details the data, assumptions, and calculations involved in developing a national-scale power system model for Sierra Leone.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Timeseries data: 2018-2050	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	[103]
The potential of Wave Energy Converters in the Galapagos islands	Galapagos Islands, Ecuador	Case study	This study evaluates the role of Wave Energy Converters (WECs) in the long-term energy transition of the Galapagos Islands. It provides an analysis of the wave energy potential (gross, sustainable, and techno-economic) in the region. Methodologically, this research introduces a novel application of the OSeMOSYS model to the Galapagos Islands, integrating WECs. The model includes detailed WEC constraints based on parallel research that examined wave patterns specific to the Galapagos and proposed an innovative WEC system tailored to the islands' conditions.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 96 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2019-2050	4 regions	1) Solar PV and wind technology have a cost advantage over other modelled technologies. However, their land use requirements present a significant challenge due to land scarcity. 2) Without subsidies, there is a general decrease in the average cost of electricity across all four islands, primarily due to the substantial increase in the cost of thermal energy driven by the prices of unsubsidized fuels. Therefore, without fuel subsidies, WECs could become more cost-competitive than thermal technology in the islands. 3) With advancements in WEC technology, specifically longer lifespans, larger capacities, and lower deployment costs, their viability could significantly improve. While WECs are not immediately essential for the Galapagos, diversifying the energy mix with multiple renewables, including WECs, offers long-term resilience, energy security, and sustainability benefits.	1) Explore additional scenarios, such as integrating geothermal and concentrated solar power. 2) Conduct detailed modelling for electric land and maritime transport, as well as other energy vectors like green hydrogen derivatives. 3) Perform a GIS-based environmental impact assessment to identify optimal WEC deployment zones that minimize impacts on the fragile ecosystems of the Galapagos.	[161]

									4) Successful electrification strategies must be coupled with energy efficiency measures to maximize environmental benefits and ensure a sustainable energy transition for the Galapagos Islands. 5) Promoting PV distributed generation and replacing diesel generation with renewables not only reduces GHG emissions but also supports conservation tourism and eliminates fuel spill risks, providing multiple benefits for the islands.		
Effect of the sustainability indicators within OSeMOSYS optimization transition scenarios	Not applicable	Modelling	This study aims to enhance energy modelling tools like OSeMOSYS by incorporating sustainability indicators, thereby providing valuable information for decision-makers. The proposed method integrates sustainability indicators into OSeMOSYS's optimization function through a multi-objective optimization process defined by correction factors associated with different indicators. Atlantis has been selected as the framework due to its comprehensive modelling of a wide range of technologies, including both renewable and non-renewable energies.	The objective function of the standard OSeMOSYS model has been adjusted to incorporate sustainability goals by adding correction factors to existing variables. For energy sustainability, the correction is made to production costs; for economic sustainability, to investment costs; and for environmental sustainability, to the penalties for pollutant emissions.	Mathematical modelling and code implementation are available at the article in the Appendix [link] Code version: MathProg	Data will be made available on request	Intrayear resolution: 6 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2014-2040	1 region	Not applicable	Not available	[151]
Long-Term Energy System Modelling for a Clean Energy Transition and Improved Energy Security in Botswana's Energy Sector Using the Open-Source Energy Modelling System	Botswana	Case study	This study aims to identify the most cost-effective pathway for Botswana's energy system to 2050, enhancing energy security while meeting the country's NDCs. Using the cost-optimization modeling tool Open-Source Energy Modelling System	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 8 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2050	1 region	1) Advocate for and facilitate the implementation of a clear, long-term strategy for renewable energy development, supported by a defined national budget. 2) Revise the Integrated Resource Plan (IRP) 2030	1) Analyze the impact of climate change on power plants and solar cells using a Climate, Land, Energy, and Water systems (CLEWS) model. 2) Evaluate the effects of increased electricity access with tools like the Open-Source Spatial	[162]

			(OSeMOSYS), the research creates least-cost pathways and incorporates constraints on emissions, fuels, capacity expansion, and power production. The study focuses on Botswana's energy system from 2015 to 2050, covering the cooking, high-heat, and transportation sectors.						renewables target to achieve more ambitious total installed capacity of renewable energy. 3) Develop financial and regulatory strategies to enable the gradual phase-out of coal and natural gas production. 4) Empower the Regulatory Authority to play an active operational role. 5) Modify the tariff-setting framework to incorporate incentive-based regulations and performance-oriented policies. 6) Expand the grid and establish a code that supports renewable power integration.	Electrification Tool (ONSSET). 3) Incorporate energy efficiency technologies across different end-use sectors.	
Techno-economic data and assumptions for open energy modelling of decarbonisation pathways in the Philippines	Philippines	Data article	This article presents an openly accessible dataset designed to support energy system modelling for decarbonization pathways in the Philippines.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Timeseries data: 2015-2050	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	[104]
Long-Term Energy System Modelling for a Clean Energy Transition in Egypt's Energy Sector	Egypt	Case study	This research used OSeMOSYS to model six scenarios, aiming to identify the technologies and policy target improvements necessary to scale up renewable energy technologies (RETs) and achieve a clean energy transition (CET) within Egypt's energy sector.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 8 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2070	1 region	1) Integrate renewable energy technologies (RETs), especially onshore wind and solar PV, into the energy system through technical, financial, and regulatory recommendations. 2) To accelerate CO2 emission reductions, revise Egypt's national renewable energy target from 42% by 2035 to 53% by 2030, as suggested by IRENA. 3) Eliminate coal as a future energy option for Egypt by adopting the COP26 mandate to phase out coal through an energy-sector ban. 4) Based on environmental and financial analyses, extend national renewable	1) Address climate system variations resulting from global warming by using a Climate, Land, Energy, and Water systems (CLEWS) model. 2) Integrate transport, electricity imports, and energy efficiency technologies into the model.	[74]

									energy targets into the latter half of the 21st century to avoid increased fossil fuel production. 5) As the number of renewable projects grows, expand the grid as needed through international bilateral projects or government financial support. 6) In conjunction with extending renewable targets, develop financial and regulatory mechanisms to phase out natural gas production.		
A Critical Analysis of Morocco's Green Hydrogen Roadmap: A Modelling Approach to Assess Country Readiness from the Energy Trilemma Perspective	Morocco	Case study	This paper seeks to thoroughly assess the least-cost pathway for integrating electrolysis-based green hydrogen into Morocco's electricity mix, using an integrated energy modeling approach. The study evaluates both the technical and economic impacts of utilizing green hydrogen for clean electricity storage and exports. While the focus is on hydrogen use within the power sector, the study excludes its applications in the transportation and industry sectors.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 8 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2015-2070	1 region	1) Replace the current "No New Coal" pledge with a "No Coal by 2030" commitment, which would involve the early decommissioning of existing coal plants. This policy would also enable the reallocation of coal subsidy funds to support wind and solar energy projects. 2) Postpone the ambitions of the roadmap and reduce the scope of its objectives. In the interim, continue using green hydrogen in ongoing projects while prioritizing investments in renewable energy rather than expanding green hydrogen to other sectors like exports and storage. 3) Strengthen financial support mechanisms to attract international funding for the electrolyser build-out aimed at export purposes, as exporting green hydrogen is more economical for Morocco than using it for local storage. 4) Combine green hydrogen storage with	1) Examine the cost curves for different storage technologies. 2) Integrate hybrid or combined systems that utilize various storage technologies. 3) Enhance the temporal resolution of the model. 4) Conduct a flexibility analysis to explore the potential for increasing renewable capacity through storage technologies, considering the associated costs and benefits. 5) Perform an environmental impact assessment with a focus on the water use of PEM electrolysers and fuel cells. 6) Incorporate sector coupling considerations, such as the use of hydrogen in the fertilizer industry.	[70]

									other available storage technologies in Morocco, such as pumped hydropower and concentrated solar power (CSP), to create a more resilient storage system.		
Open energy system modelling for low-emission hydrogen roadmap planning: The case of Colombia	Colombia	Case study	This study provides a techno-economic evaluation of hydrogen pathways and their interactions across different sectors within the Colombian energy system. Using the open energy system optimization framework OSeMOSYS, we modelled an extensive supply-demand hydrogen chain and explored a range of scenarios from 2021 to 2050, including a sensitivity analysis.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 1 timeslice Modelling horizon: 2021-2070	1 region	1) Continue designing regulations to promote the development of low-emission hydrogen projects over the coming years to ensure a steady expansion of installed capacity. 2) Develop robust policies to support the exploitation of Colombia's natural gas reserves, which is crucial for the implementation of a national hydrogen strategy. 3) Incentivize not only hydrogen production but also the adoption of hydrogen-based technologies in end-use sectors, particularly industry and transport, with special focus on developing sustainable fuels for heavy-duty, air, and maritime sectors. 4) Strengthen research and development in biomass gasification to complement the hydrogen supply. 5) Create a national CCUS roadmap to define strategies for deploying infrastructure, CO2 trading, and end-use agreements within an integrated ecosystem for CO2 utilization and storage.	1) Broaden the model to include a multiregional assessment, providing insights into the geographical implications and optimal locations for projects. 2) Explore an integrated assessment that incorporates land use, waste management, and industrial processes to better understand the interactions between the hydrogen chain and non-energy sectors. 3) Analyze ammonia, methanol, and other hydrogen carriers separately to uncover alternative uses for low-emission hydrogen. 4) Assess fiscal revenues, job transitions, economic growth, and distributional effects to develop a more comprehensive strategy for implementing the hydrogen roadmap. 5) Investigate the impact of uncertainties in modelling parameters to strengthen the reliability of our policy recommendations. 6) Engage stakeholders in discussions to incorporate more realistic assumptions and business perspectives.	[34]
Air quality and health co-benefits of low carbon transition policies in electricity system: the case of Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region	Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region, China	Case study - Methodology	This study estimates the impacts of low carbon transition policies on the electricity system in the BTH area through 2060. This includes analyzing one BAU scenario, six single	Not applicable	Not applicable	Supplementary material available at [link]	Intrayear resolution: 16 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2020-2060	Not available	1) Enhance research and development to overcome technologies that minimize energy use in power generation, transmission, and distribution, and to boost	Evaluate the policy costs associated with each instrument proposed in each scenario.	[134]

			scenarios, and five combined scenarios. Using an open-source energy modelling system and an extended response surface model (ERSM), we evaluate the effects on installed power capacity, CO2 emissions, air quality, and human health.						the available capacity of power plants. 2) Promote the advancement of energy storage and distributed energy resources configurations to meet increasing electricity demand, which is vital for the sustainable development of the electric system. 3) To improve carbon reduction and achieve 'dual carbon' objectives, policymakers should focus on integrating renewable energy, technical innovation, CCUS, and transitioning from gas to electricity. 4) The power generation sector should expedite efforts to increase CCUS units, improve low-carbon technology innovation, and carry out CCUS technology demonstration projects. 5) Local governments should implement supportive policies and regulatory frameworks, and accelerate the advancement of hydrogen energy and low-speed wind power generation. 6) Higher PM2.5 concentrations projected for Hebei in 2060 compared to Beijing and Tianjin, under all decarbonization scenarios, indicate the need for additional air quality control measures. End-of-pipe pollution controls for fuel-related power generation systems in Hebei should be included. 7) Recommend regionally tailored decarbonization policies for air pollution control.	
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<p>Depreciating currency impacts on local-scale energy system planning: The case study of Accra, Ghana</p>	<p>Accra, Ghana</p>	<p>Case study</p>	<p>This work develops cost scenarios to account for local currency depreciation in Accra, Ghana, and evaluates its impacts on long-term energy system planning using the open-source energy system optimization model (ESOM), OSeMOSYS. The scenarios consider various exchange rate developments of the Ghanaian cedi (GHS) against the US dollar (USD), affecting technology investment and energy carrier costs. Regression models are employed to quantify the influence of foreign exchange rates on import commodity costs in Ghana.</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>	<p>Data will be made available on request</p>	<p>Intrayear resolution: 24 timeslices Modelling horizon: 2020 to 2050 in 5-year time steps,</p>	<p>1 region</p>	<p>1) Evaluating the potential impacts of currency depreciation on energy planning is crucial for developing effective, resilient, and sustainable long-term energy strategies. 2) In Accra, the effects of currency depreciation are significant across all scenarios. As depreciation increases, investments in renewable energy technologies (RETs) may decrease substantially in cost-optimal solutions, leading to a greater reliance on the national electricity grid. 3) The reduction in RET investments due to rising depreciation has important implications for developing cities and countries striving to meet global CO2 emission reduction targets. 4) Price protections and additional support policies may be necessary within international markets and sustainability agreements to bolster RET investments in the Global South. 5) If photovoltaic (PV) systems are part of broader sustainability commitments in Accra, it is advisable to make these investments earlier in the planning horizon to ensure cost-effective deployment. 6) Cost-optimal investment decisions in waste-to-energy combined heat and power (CCP) remain relatively resilient to currency depreciation. Thus, waste energy presents a lower-</p>	<p>1) Integrate uncertainty quantification techniques. 2) Add more detailed data for specific energy system components, such as grid infrastructure costs and detailed information on electrical appliances within each sector.</p>	<p>[63]</p>
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									risk and effective RET option for Accra's energy transition, even under uncertain exchange rate conditions.		
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* The article was not included in the bibliometric analysis but was identified as an important contributor to the current OSeMOSYS code.